

THE ART OF SELECTING ADEQUATE MOVEMENT

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*‘Wie niet in beweging komt,
merkt zijn eigen ketenen niet op’
Rosa Luxemburg (1871–1919)*

VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT

The Art of Selecting Adequate Movement

ACADEMISCH PROEFSCHRIFT

ter verkrijging van de graad Doctor
aan de Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam,
op gezag van de rector magnificus
prof.dr. V. Subramaniam,
in het openbaar te verdedigen
ten overstaan van de promotiecommissie van de
Faculteit der Gedrags- en Bewegingswetenschappen
op vrijdag 10 januari 2020 om 11.45 uur
in de aula van de universiteit,
De Boelelaan 1105

door

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geboren te Amsterdam

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Chapter 1

General introduction

For all living organisms, it is crucial to adapt their behaviour to a challenging and constantly changing environment. In order to do so, animals developed the ability to actively change body segments to new positions and orientations (also known as to move). This feature enables them to react rapidly to sudden threats, such as abrupt temperature changes in the environment, and to modify their surroundings for their own benefits, such as moving to a food source. However, solely the ability to move is not sufficient for meaningful interactions with the environment; in addition, perceiving the world around them is a prerequisite for making adequate behaviour (von Helmholtz, 1867; Gibson, 1958). As such, woodlice move faster when they are in an undesirable warm environment, a honeybee can find her way towards a flower, and a chameleon can intercept flies with his tongue. For these animals, this behaviour is inherited from past generations and is a product of millions of generational iterations. Hence, the described behaviour is to an extent hardwired in the nervous system of these animals. As such, a woodlouse reacts solely to the information that the environment is perceived as too warm, and starts to move faster “hoping” to get away from this dreadful situation. Bees, on the other hand, as well as chameleons, can modify this inherited behaviour by learning from past exposures (Cheng and Wignall, 2005).

Similarly to honeybees and chameleons, we humans, have the ability to modify movement patterns and behaviours (Dennett, 2017). Instant movement and behavioural adjustments requires us to learn from past events and store relevant information in our memory. This again can be recalled, and when a similar event occurs, we predict outcomes of planned movements and behave accordingly to minimise erroneous movement outcomes (von Helmholtz, 1867). This implies that

we have to make judgments on how (and whether) a movement pattern should be executed. Hence, adequate movement behaviour relies on selecting a pattern that overcomes the task requirement while keeping the biomechanical demands within limits of the physical ability. From this, we can deduce that knowledge of the own physical limits – or in other words, one’s perceived ability – should be integrated into the human motor control.

The process of judging whether and how a task should be performed is already visible at a very early stage of our lives. Adolph and Eppler (1998) demonstrated that infants, after a critical age, placed at a high end of a slope only moved down the slope when they were able to descend safely and that the ability to judge slopes improved over weeks. This learning process continues after childhood by updating the knowledge we have of our physical abilities and skills, as illustrated in different sports disciplines (Chamberlain et al., 1993; Williams and Ericsson, 2005; Williams and Ford, 2008). Hence, exposure to a diverse set of activities embeds the latest knowledge of the status of the physical abilities, which is beneficial for judgement abilities to meet task requirements, leading to the selection of an adequate motor behaviour.

1.1 Selecting adequate movement behaviour

To understand this process of selecting adequate movement strategy it might be insightful to capture this process in a simplified model, as models can help to formulate new hypotheses and help to understand flaws in the system. In this thesis, a theoretical model will guide us through the chapters and will be used as a backbone to interpret the results.

Figure 1.1 displays a graphical interpretation of this model, consisting of a number of constructs that seem relevant in the process. Every arrow in this framework depicts an information stream from one construct to another. Some of the constructs need to be formed prior to every new movement task, whereas other constructs are established for longer periods. If a construct is task-specific, and thus constructed when a new task arises, this is indicated by *(i)*. Derived from computing and programming disciplines, an iteration, *i* is one repetition out of many cycles, in which a programme is executed and repeated with different input within each iteration.

When we face a challenging, behavioural motor task, such as *crossing a busy street on a bicycle*, one of the first aspects that is necessary for an adequate action, is appropriate perception of the requirements of the task at hand (see [1] in Figure 1.1) (Gibson, 1958, 2002; Konczak et al., 1992). In this specific example, the cyclist

Figure 1.1: *The proposed model of the interplay between the perceived ability, perceived task requirements, and actual ability and how this determines the probability of success of a motor task.*

will deal with estimations along the following lines:

What power should I apply on the pedals to cross the street, what is the efficiency of my bike, is there a heavy wind blowing, what is the distance and time available to cross the street, before the approaching taxi is at my position?

After we formed an idea on what is needed for successfully overcoming the task requirements, we need to judge whether we have the physical ability (i.e., anthropometrics, muscle strength, and coordination [2]) to meet these requirements (Warren, 1984; Mark and Vogeleson, 1987), as such we form a perception of our ability [3]. Hence, we ask ourselves:

Can my legs produce the estimated required power?

On the basis of the answers to these questions, we make a behavioural choice and select an accompanying motor strategy [4]. This consists of the choice whether and how a motor action should be performed, and the movement pattern that will be selected if we decide to proceed. In my example:

Shall I cross the street now or would it be safer not to, and if I go, would it be more efficient to push off the ground before I start applying forces on the pedals, or should I immediately start, standing on the pedals, to generate the maximum amount of power.

Our resulting selected behaviour will pass through a “filter” of actual ability and actual task requirements to “check” to which extent the task requirements are fulfilled. Hence, the quality of the initial perception determines the probability of successfully executing the motor task [5].

This probability of success will be used as an input to update the state of the overall perceived ability [6]. However, similar to other learning processes, the rate of learning will depend on the outcome of the previous action, and if the outcome was not very dramatic it might need some iterations to notice a change in behaviour. Thus, the change in perceived ability due to the newly received information will be small.

At times when the knowledge of the self is not aligned with one’s actual physical abilities, erroneous behaviour of consequence might occur. In terms of movement behaviour, such misjudgment may lead to excessive risk-taking or needlessly avoiding activities. For most people this judgment is mostly reasonably adequate; yet, for a subset of the population, the perceived ability and the task biomechanical requirements may be more diffuse than for others.

1.2 Ageing and appropriate judgment in older adults

With ageing, the perceived and actual ability might start diverging, which may lead to less adequate motor behaviour. Firstly, the origin of this divergence could be explained by the age-related decline in physical abilities, such as decreased muscle force and function, and sensory acuity (Spiriduso, 1995; Lord et al., 2007). Individuals should be aware of those changes, as when this decrease stays unnoticed it enhances the divergence of the perceived and actual ability. Secondly, the cognitive abilities are subjected to ageing too (Salthouse, 2009): comprehending a decrease in working memory (Hasher et al., 1988; Salthouse and Kersten, 1993), attentional resources (Woollacott and Shumway-Cook, 2002), neural plasticity (Burke and Barnes, 2006), and processing speed (Salthouse, 1996, 2000); possibly making it even more difficult to calibrate the perceived ability with the actual physical ability.

Interestingly, Delbaere et al. (2010a) performed a study that accentuated the influence of the disparity between physiological and perceived fall risk on prospective falls. They assessed the perceived fall risk by measuring the concern of falling by using the falls efficacy scale international (FESi): a 16-item questionnaire which is a reliable and validated instrument that has found its way to the clinic. This perceived fall risk was compared with the physical profile assessment, providing a quantification of the individual's physical fall risk. Their results suggested that one-third of older adults over- or underestimated their fall risk. Moreover, Butler et al. (2015) found that fall risk was increased in older individuals that would select behaviour that was likely to exceed their physical ability. Yet, it is not well understood through which mechanisms the misalignment between perceived and physiological fall risk has its effect on falls in older adults. In this thesis, we formulate a mechanism using the framework shown in figure 1.1.

1.3 Aim and outline of the thesis

The overall aim of this thesis is to develop methods and paradigms to assess the interplay between perceived and actual ability and its relation to the outcome of a motor task to understand how adequate movements are produced. To do so, a set of studies are conducted to understand and measure the relation between different facets of the proposed model (Figure 1.1). The focus of this thesis will be on older adults, as a substantial set of older individuals may experience problems with aligning the perceived and actual ability.

In the first experiment, described in **chapter 2**, we investigate whether the

perceived and actual ability align in older adults by evaluating their gait ability. In doing so, we assume that there is a direct relationship between the perceived and actual ability, and ignore behavioural choice. Furthermore, we propose novel quantitative measures that assess the degree of misjudgment. To translate this to our theoretical framework, we evaluate the discrepancy between the *perceived ability (i)* [3] and the *actual ability (i)* [2].

In **chapter 3** we compare multiple tasks to elicit the task dependency of the perceived ability, actual ability, and the disparity between these two terms. Moreover, criteria are introduced for the development of a valid tasks to assess misjudgment. The framework's components that is studied in this chapter, is the relation between the *perceived ability* (overall perceived ability,[6]) and *perceived ability (i)* (task dependent perceived ability, [3]).

In the next three chapters, the focus is shifted from the perceived ability to the behaviour choice by studying the strategy selection while stepping down a height difference. The aim of **chapter 4** is to unravel whether the selected *behaviour choice* [4] corresponds to one's *actual ability (i)* [2]. This is studied by comparing expected stepping down with unexpected stepping down. In this paradigm the expected stepping down reflects the behavioural choice as this condition allows the integration of the perceived and actual ability prior to the stepping down. In the unexpected condition, the reactive behaviour does not allow for any forward planning, hence its performance solely relies on the actual physical ability.

In **chapter 5**, the aim is to understand the role of anxiety in strategy selection, and how older participants change their strategy selection in a stepping down task when the consequence of erroneous behaviour is increased. I expect the participant to perform safer behaviour when we increase the consequence. In our framework, it is less obvious where the level of consequence interact with the other facets. However, I believe that the task consequence is weighted in the formation of a perception of the task requirements. To illustrate this, when walking at ground level next to a kerb the stakes of erroneous behaviour are rather small, hence there is a certain probability that you select an erroneous movement (let's say 1 out of million steps). However, when you are walking next to the edge of a deep cliff you are likely to lower this probability, hence the chances of selecting an erroneous movement are even less (maybe 1 out of 100 million steps). Therefore, it is likely that the *perceived task requirements* will be different from a less threatening situation (e.g., as you will prefer a smaller gait pattern to lower the chances of stepping over the cliff's edge).

Then, in the last experiment in **chapter 6**, I investigate whether the adequateness of the *behavioural choice*[4] truly prescribes the *probability of success*[5]. As

adequate behaviour result in a higher probability of success, one is less likely to fall in the upcoming months. Hence, the power to discriminate fallers from non-fallers using the behavioural choice as a function of the actual physical ability is tested.

Finally, the findings of this dissertation will be elaborated in the general discussion in **chapter 7**. The results will be synthesised to evaluate our hypothesis theoretical framework.

Chapter 2

The Degree of Misjudgment Between Perceived and Actual Gait Ability in Older Adults

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2.1 Abstract

Successful execution of motor tasks requires an integration of the perception of one's physical abilities and the perception of the task itself. Physical and cognitive decline associated with ageing may lead to misjudgments of these perceived and actual abilities and possibly to errors that may lead to balance loss. We aimed to directly quantify the degree to which older adults misjudge their actual gait ability. Twenty-seven older adults participated and were instructed to walk on a narrow path projected on a treadmill. We tested two paradigms to estimate the participants' perceived gait ability: a path width manipulation, in which participants had to indicate the smallest path width that they could walk on without stepping outside or losing balance (at given speed), and a treadmill speed manipulation, in which they had to indicate the maximum speed that they could use at given path width. We determined their actual ability as the probability of stepping inside the path over a range of path widths and speeds. The path width paradigm seemed suitable for evaluating self-perception of actual gait ability and revealed that participants appeared to show a range of misjudgment towards either over- or underestimating their actual abilities. Better abilities appeared not associated with better judgment. Direct quantification of the degree of misjudgment provides insight in the interplay between cognition and physical abilities and can

The contents of this chapter have been published in *Gait & Posture*

be of added value towards prevention of falls and promotion of healthy ageing.

2.2 Introduction

For optimal motor performance, we need to predict the results of our motor actions in different circumstances. This predictive ability requires estimation of one's own physical abilities. Although this knowledge is not always perfect (Kruger and Dunning, 1999), in most cases we are nevertheless able to make an educated guess whether execution of a planned task can be performed successfully. Already at a young age, infants learn whether or not to move down a slope based on their locomotor abilities (Adolph and Eppler, 1998). At the other side of the age spectrum, physical decline (Woollacott and Shumway-Cook, 2002; Vandervoort, 2002; Segev-Jacobovski et al., 2011) requires accompanying adjustment of the perception of these abilities to select the appropriate motor strategy in view of the motor task requirements. This adjustment might even be all the more challenging due to the age-related brain changes such as reduced neural plasticity (VanSwearingen and Studenski, 2014; Lustig et al., 2009) and cognitive functioning (Segev-Jacobovski et al., 2011). Erroneous perception of one's own physical abilities or of the task requirements could lead to excessive risk-taking on the one hand (Butler et al., 2015), or needles avoidance of activities on the other hand (Delbaere et al., 2004).

Almost one-third of the older adults misjudged their physiological fall risk (Delbaere et al., 2010a). Age-related perceptual (mis)judgement of physical abilities has further been studied in gait related tasks. For example in aperture crossing, older adults rotate their shoulders more compared to young adults (Hackney and Cinelli, 2011, 2013) and in stair climbing, older participants appear more likely to choose a step height which matches their maximum achievable step height than their younger peers (Konczak et al., 1992), suggesting that estimates on physical capacities are adjusted with ageing. Nevertheless, 20 percent of the observed older persons overestimated their maximum step height, whereas 10 percent underestimated their maximum achievable step height (Konczak et al., 1992). Sakurai et al. (2013) compared the estimated and actual height for stepping over a bar and found that 18 percent of the older adults overestimated the bar height that they could overstep. These studies mainly tested perception of abilities limited by physical dimensions, such as shoulder width or leg length.

The relation between physical ability and perceived ability regarding balance control has been studied by Butler and co-workers (Butler et al., 2015) in plank crossing. They investigated the behavioural risk that older adults were willing to take by comparing individuals' selected plank width with the probability to

make errors on this width measured during over ground walking. They found that persons whose behavioural risk matched their physical ability were less likely to experience a fall in the forthcoming year than their peers who took higher risks (Butler et al., 2015). However, participants chose a plank to cross but were not actually allowed to cross it. The chosen plank width was compared with the stepping accuracy on an 18-cm wide path at ground level. Perceptual judgment may in this design be affected by plank height or length, and for actual ability ceiling effects may have occurred given the fixed path width.

We aimed to directly quantify the agreement of older adults' perceptual judgment and their actual ability in a daily life task (i.e., walking). We propose two paradigms of testing actual gait ability: a path width manipulation and a speed manipulation and asked participants to indicate the smallest path width (at given speed) and maximum speed (at given path width) at which they believed they could accurately perform, i.e., walk without stepping outside the path or losing balance. These manipulations were expected to affect step accuracy during gait. Narrowing the path width reduces the base of support and a more strict control of the centre of mass movement is needed to successfully complete the task (Arvin et al., 2016; Schragger et al., 2008). Older adults have also been shown to decrease gait speed when walking on a narrow path (Schragger et al., 2008; Deshpande and Zhang, 2014), suggesting that more time is needed in narrow base walking for more strict control of foot placement. For both path width and speed manipulations, the perceived and actual abilities can be determined and compared to provide insight into the older adult's degree of misjudgment. Since one-third of older adults misjudges their fall risk (Delbaere et al., 2010a), we expected no strong correlation between the perceived and actual gait ability. Furthermore, since sport experts are more accurate at judging their capabilities than their less expert peers (Williams and Ericsson, 2005; Williams and Ford, 2008), we hypothesised that older adults with better gait performance levels judge their actual abilities better than those performing less.

2.3 Material & methods

Participants

Twenty-seven older adults (74.4 SD 5.6 years, 16 females) participated. Persons who had a mini mental state examination (MMSE) score of 24 or lower, were not able to walk continuously and without walking aid for 10 minutes, reported any musculoskeletal or neurological impairments or major trauma in the last year, or took medication which could have affected their gait stability, were excluded from

participation. All participants signed an informed consent, which was approved by the local research ethics committee (#2015-50).

Protocol

Before the gait ability test, we assessed participants' self-efficacy (Kempen et al., 2007), using the Dutch version of the Falls Efficacy Scale International (FESi, Yardley et al. (2005)) and their physical capacities by measuring grip strength (A5401-Digital Hand Grip Strength Dynamometer, Take, Niigata, Japan) and knee extension strength (MicroFET 2, Hoggan Health Industries, Draper, UT).

Participants were familiarised with walking on a large, motor-driven treadmill at a speed of 1.11 m/s (S-Mill, Forcelink, Culemborg, The Netherlands; length x width: 4x3 m) for at least three minutes or longer if considered necessary by the participant or experimenter. A projector (CP-X5022WN, Hitachi, Tokyo, Japan) projected in the walking direction on the treadmill a visual path; a yellow rectangle of which the width could be varied while the virtual path length was always 20 meter, irrespective of speed. Participants wore a safety harness, attached by ropes to the ceiling. First, the self-perceived path width performance ($Width_{perc}$) was determined by instructing the participants to indicate the narrowest path width they perceived they could walk on without stepping outside the path's boundaries, at the speed they experienced during the familiarisation period. This procedure was done on a stationary treadmill, by scrolling the scroll-wheel of a handheld computer mouse to adjust the width of the projected path, and repeated four times and randomised in two directions, by broadening a path starting at 0.05 m and narrowing a path starting at 0.50 m. Secondly, the actual path width was determined by subjecting the participants to 3 repetitions of 5 randomised paths widths (0.120, 0.144, 0.160, 0.178, 0.200 m) while walking at a speed of 1.11 m/s. There was at least 10 meters without projection before a new path was presented. Thirdly, the participants walked at 1.11 m/s, and a 0.16x0.16 m square was projected 1.50 m in front of them for 10 seconds. Then the projection disappeared and the treadmill simultaneously switched to a self-paced mode. This mode allowed participants to control their own gait speed by speeding up or slowing down. The algorithm the treadmill obeyed was conform equation 2.1 ((Sloot et al., 2014) for details). This equation is based on a standard PD-controller and controls the belt using participant's position (x) and gait speed (\dot{x}). The parameters K_x and $K_{\dot{x}}$ are respectively a position-gain and a speed-gain, and were set at 0.6 and 1.2.

$$\ddot{x} = K_x \cdot \Delta x - K_{\dot{x}} \cdot \dot{x} \cdot \Delta x \quad (2.1)$$

Participants were instructed to adjust their speed as soon as the square disappeared and indicate the fastest speed they believed they could walk without stepping outside the path at the previously indicated path width. Prior to this speed manipulation, participants were given the opportunity to familiarise again for at least 3 minutes with the self-paced mode of the treadmill. The mean speed of four repetitions was used to determine the self-perceived speed (v_{perc}). Finally, we determined the actual speed (v_{act}) by asking the participants to walk on paths of a fixed width of 0.16 m for 3 repetitions at 5 different speeds (0.83, 0.97, 1.11, 1.25, 1.39 m/s). The order of speeds was randomised over subjects and for each speed, the participants performed 3 paths before the speed changed. In all experimental testing participants walked without any assistive walking device.

Figure 2.1: A Gaussian probability curve was fitted on the mediolateral positions of the middle of the foot. The middle of the foot was calculated from the pointed positions indicated in the box in the figure. The area underneath this curve and which is covered by the virtual path is the probability of success and denoted by $P(\text{path})$. The hypothetical path width which covers 90% of the probability curve was computed and coined Width_{act} . The peak of the probability curve represents the average mediolateral foot position and is not in the middle of the path per se. These procedures were adapted from a study by Butler and co-workers (2014).

Data acquisition and analysis

Feet and pelvis kinematics were measured using an OptoTrak motion capture system (Northern Digital Inc., Ontario, Canada). Three rigid clusters with three infrared light emitting diodes each, were placed on the participant's heels and lower back and were captured by a 2x3 camera array. The feet were considered as rigid segments and a pointer was used to indicate the outer boundaries of the shoe (Figure. 1) as well as the position of the projected path in space. Separate pointer recordings were combined to express the projected path and foot markers in global coordinates (Zatsiorsky, 2002). Gait events (toe-offs and heel strikes) were automatically detected from the kinematic data (Hreljac and Marshall, 2000), and visually checked. From these boundaries (Figure. 2.1), the positions of the middle of the foot at mid-stance were determined. A Gaussian probability curve was fitted to the mediolateral mid-stance foot position data. This enabled the computation of the probability of successfully stepping with the entire foot inside the projected path ($P(path)$, Figure. 2.1) according to Butler et al. (2015). Following this calculation, $P(path)$ depended on the combination of step width, step width variability, and the mean mediolateral foot position. For our proposed manipulation to be useful to determine the degree of misjudgment, $P(path)$ had to be related to path width or speed, which was the case for the path width but not for the speed manipulation. Therefore only for the path width manipulation, the best actual performance was calculated ($Width_{act}$). This was defined as the path width that would contain 90% of all steps based on the distribution of step widths in the best trial ($Width_{act}$); Figure 2.1). Subsequently, the association between $Width_{perc}$ and $Width_{act}$ was calculated and the degree of misjudgment was determined by the vertical distance to the identity line for this association. A negative score indicated underestimation of one's ability, while a positive score indicated overestimation. Since strength and FESi score are indicative for respectively actual and perceived ability, we used these measures to validate the perceived and actual ability components of the degree of misjudgment. Analyses were performed using MATLAB R2015b (Mathworks, Natick, MA).

Statistical Analysis

First, to evaluate the effects of manipulations on $P(path)$, step width, and step width variability repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. Mauchly's test showed a violation of sphericity for $P(path)$ ($W=0.226$, $p<0.001$) and step width variability ($W=0.442$, $p=0.017$) for the path width manipulation, and step width ($W= 0.379$, $p=0.038$) for the speed manipulation, thus for these measures a

Greenhouse Geiser correction ($P(path)$: $\epsilon=0.572$, step width variability: $\epsilon=0.725$, step width: $\epsilon=0.744$) was applied. Post-hoc paired t-tests with Bonferroni adjustment were used on significant main effects. Further analyses were restricted to the path width manipulation as only this significantly affected gait accuracy.

The scores on the FESi were compared with the perceived ability using a Spearman's rank correlation rho with Monte-Carlo resampling. This test was used because the scores on the FESi were not normally distributed ($W=0.801$, $p<0.001$). The consistency over the four repetitions of indicating self-perceived ability ($Width_{perc}$) was assessed using an intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC).

To investigate associations between $Width_{act}$ and physical capacities (knee extension strength and grip strength) or $Width_{act}$, linear regression analysis was used for knee extension strength and a Spearman's rank correlation rho with Monte-Carlo resampling was used for grip strength and for $Width_{act}$ as these were not normally distributed (grip strength: $W=0.918$, $p=0.035$, $Width_{perc}$: $W=0.922$, $p=0.030$).

Finally, to test whether the degree of judgment was dependent on the actual ability ($Width_{act}$) a Spearman's rank correlation rho with Monte-Carlo resampling was used because the absolute degree of misjudgment was not normally distributed ($W=0.876$, $p=0.004$).

Statistical software (R, version 3.1.1, <http://www.r-project.org/>) was used to perform the statistical analysis. Additionally, the coin package (Hothorn et al., 2006) was used for the implementation of the Monte-Carlo resampling procedure. For all statistical testing, the level of significance was set at 0.05.

2.4 Results

$P(path)$ was on average 0.80 ± 0.36 over all path widths and 0.86 ± 0.10 over all speeds (Figure 2.4 and Table 2.1). Repeated measures ANOVA revealed a main effect of path width on $P(path)$ ($F(2.29, 59.51)=24.779$, $p<0.001$) and on step width ($F(4,96)=11.513$, $p<0.001$). Post-hoc analysis showed that $P(path)$ values on the narrowest and broadest path widths were significantly different from all other path widths (Figure 2.4a). Step width on the narrowest path significantly differed from the three most broad paths, and the step width on the broadest path width was significantly wider from those on the other paths except 0.160 m (Figure 2.4c). $P(path)$ was not significantly affected by speed ($F(4,96)=1.377$, $p=0.248$, Figure 2.4b).

ICCs showed that the test-retest reliability of testing $Width_{perc}$ was fairly high (ICC=0.877). However, this perceived ability estimate ($Width_{perc}$) was not asso-

Table 2.1: *Descriptive statistics of outcome measures. Prevalence with percentage of sample or mean values with standard deviation (SD) are shown (mean(SD)). When a measure is not normally distributed the median and interquartile range (IQR) are given, indicated by the square brackets (median[IQR]).*

Descriptives:			
Age	74.4	(5.64)	years
Medication (≥ 4 different medicines)	6	(22%)	persons
Higher educated participants	16	(59%)	persons
Fallers (≥ 2 falls in the past year)	6	(22%)	persons
Falls in the past year	1	[1]	falls
MMSE	28	[2]	points
FESi	18	[3.75]	points
Grip strength	290	[130]	N
Knee extension force	322	(76)	N
Body mass index	26.1	(3.7)	$\frac{kg}{m^2}$
Path width manipulation:			
Width _{perc}	0.24	[0.17]	m
Width _{act}	0.16	(0.056)	m
$P(path)$	0.80	(0.13)	
Speed manipulation:			
v_{perc}	1.35	(0.23)	$\frac{m}{s}$
$P(path)$	0.86	(0.10)	
Degree of misjudgment:			
Total	-0.07	(0.105)	m
Absolute	0.07	[0.110]	m

ciated with the score on the FESi ($\rho=0.063$, $p=0.750$).

Actual ability (Width_{act}) was negatively correlated with knee extension strength ($F(1,25)=13.460$, $p=0.001$, $R^2=0.350$, Figure. 2.3a), but was not associated with grip strength ($\rho=-0.142$, $p=0.479$, Figure 2.3b). No significant association was found between Width_{perc} and Width_{act} ($\rho=0.310$, $p=0.115$, Figure 2.2a), indicating no relation between perceived and actual ability. The scatter plot of Width_{perc} and Width_{act} also clearly shows different degrees of misjudgment between participants. A Shapiro-Wilk's test of normality showed that the degree of misjudgment was approximately normally distributed ($W=0.961$, $p=0.397$, Figure. 2.2b), with a skewness of -0.543 ($SE_{skew}=0.448$) and a kurtosis of -0.319 ($SE_{kurt}=0.872$). Performance did not influence on the absolute degree of misjudgment ($\rho=-0.088$, $p=0.650$), indicating that judgment of gait accuracy was not dependent on actual ability.

Figure 2.2: *Degree of misjudgment.* **a)** The perceived and actual ability displayed for every participant (blue circle). The degree of misjudgment was calculated by subtracting the $Width_{perc}$ from the $Width_{act}$. **b)** Degree of misjudgment. Perfect agreement of the two measures will lead to no misjudgment or a score of zero. A positive score inclines overestimating, where a negative score inclines underestimating.

Figure 2.3: *Peak strength versus the path width with a 90% chance of success ($Width_{act}$).* **a)** Participants with a higher normalised knee extension strength were more likely to have a smaller $Width_{act}$, this effect was significant ($F(1,25)=13.5$, $p=0.001$). **b)** Generated grip strength versus $Width_{act}$.

2.5 Discussion

A narrower path width led to more errors than a wider path width, as expected but gait accuracy was not influenced by speed (Figure 2.4b). Although we expected accuracy to decrease with increasing speed, path width and path width variability did not change over speeds on the group level. Possibly, this can be explained by a quadratical relation between step width and walking speed (i.e., following a U-

shape) (Helbostad and Moe-Nilssen, 2003), where the smallest step width occurs near the preferred walking speed. For the speed manipulation, a fixed range of speeds was imposed, and thus for each participant different relative speeds in terms of preferred walking speed might have effaced the individual effects of step width and step width variability and therefore accuracy. Relating gait accuracy to preferred walking speed could help understand this relationship, however preferred walking speed might be influenced by one's perceived ability.

The two components of the degree of misjudgment were compared to FESi and the strength measures to explore the validity of these components. The significant correlation between knee extension force and $Width_{act}$ suggests that $Width_{act}$ is a suitable measure of the participants' actual capacities. Moreover, Shin et al. (2012) showed that wider steps were related to lower leg strength, suggesting that step width reflects one's actual ability. $Width_{perc}$ was not related to FESi, which might suggest that $Width_{perc}$ was not a suitable measure, yet it can be questioned whether FESi was an appropriate and sensitive variable to verify self-perception of motor capacities in our sample. Despite a large range in knee extension strength in our sample, and grip strength values within normal bounds of the general population (Desrosiers et al., 1995), the range for FESi scores was only 16-27 out of a maximum score of 64, which was lower than the mean score of 28 points in a larger sample of the Dutch population (Kempen et al., 2007). ICC values showed that participants were very consistent in indicating their perceived abilities over the four repetitions, suggesting that participants had a well defined perception of what they thought they were able to accomplish, although this could also be a consequence of a tendency of participants to be consistent (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

We expected that participants with good physical abilities to be more accurate in their judgment than those with low abilities. Although not studied in gait, Williams and Ericsson (2005) reviewed several perceptual-cognitive experiments and argued that experts had better decision making skills than their less expert peers. In contrast, we found no evidence for this in our results. Given our inclusion criteria, all our participants had ample experience in walking and still were physically active in gait activities, to be considered experts in this sub-maximal and common motor task.

Actual gait ability was quantified based on $Width_{act}$, allowing 10% of erroneous steps. This choice of 90% was rather arbitrary and a more conservative value, for example 95%, shifts the distribution of the degree of misjudgment (Figure 2.2b) to the right, leading to more participants underestimating their abilities than we currently observed. In comparison, in stepping over obstacles this parameter was set at 100% (Sakurai et al., 2013). Several studies showed the shortcoming of some

older adults to accurately perceive their actual ability (Butler et al., 2015; Delbaere et al., 2010a; Sakurai et al., 2013), this notion is supported by our results.

Practical usability of the degree of misjudgment to pinpoint potentially harmful consequences in older adults, depends on how this measure translates to other daily life tasks. O'Brien and Ahmed (2013) demonstrated that young adults consistently showed either risky or risk-averse movement behaviour in two different motor tasks. Likewise, it can be assumed that the degree of misjudgment generalises to other daily life activities.

Our objective was to quantify the misjudgment of walking ability in older adults. Such quantification allows direct comparison of the perceived and actual performance, thereby quantifying the degree of misjudgment on a continuous scale. Such a measure has been emphasised to be useful to include in fall risk assessments (Delbaere et al., 2010a) and allow better personalised interventions. However, it is still unknown at which value the misjudgment becomes problematic.

2.5.1 Conclusions

Older adults' judgment of their gait ability in terms of accuracy can be evaluated by a path width paradigm. Accuracy seemed a good estimate of physical capacities such as leg strength, and although no clear relation with a representative golden standard, $Width_{perc}$ is assumed to represent the perceived ability. Our proposed degree of misjudgment directly quantifies older individual's misjudgment between perceived and actual gait ability, irrespective of their performance level.

Figure 2.4: Probability of stepping inside the path ($P(\text{path})$) versus the path width and speed manipulation. **a)** Mean $P(\text{path})$ on the path width manipulation (error bars represent standard deviations), which appeared affected by path width. **b)** Mean $P(\text{path})$ on the different speeds, which was not affected by speed. **c)** Mean step width versus path width on a fixed speed (1.11 m/s). **d)** Mean step width versus speed with fixed path width (0.160 m). **e)** Mean step width variability versus path width. **f)** Mean step width variability versus speed. Significant main differences are indicated by diamonds ($p < 0.05$). Post-hoc differences between adjacent levels ($p < 0.05$) are indicated by asterisks.

Chapter 3

On the validity and consistency of misjudgment of stepping ability in young and older adults

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3.1 Abstract

Disparities between perceived and actual physical abilities have been shown in older adults and may lead to balance loss or falls. However, it is unclear whether one's misjudgment is an inherent trait and thus consistent across different tasks, and whether this misjudgment is age-related. We measured the degree of misjudgment in young and older adults on four different stepping tasks; stepping over a raised bar, crossing a declining cord by stepping over it at a self-selected height, crossing a virtual river by stepping over it at a self-selected width, and making a recovery step after release from an inclined position. Before comparison, we carefully checked the validity of the different tasks to determine the misjudgment. No substantial differences were found in the amplitude of the misjudgment between the age groups, and the degree of misjudgment did not transfer across different stepping tasks. However, since only one task (i.e., stepping over a raised bar) met our criteria for validly assessing one's misjudgment, it remains unclear whether the degree of misjudgment is task-specific or an inherent trait. These findings stress the importance of testing the construct validity of the task, prior to the examination of the misjudgment of stepping ability.

The contents of this chapter have been published in PLoS ONE

3.2 Introduction

Motor actions allow humans to interact with the environment, however, there is a rich variety of movements that can fulfill the same motor task (Bernstein, 1967). The selection process, or planning of a motor task is crucial for success of the action (von Helmholtz, 1962). Recent studies showed that the selection process depends on one's perceived ability to perform the intended action (Fajen, 2005; Witt and Proffitt, 2008; Lessard et al., 2009). This entails that one's ability must be judged prior to the selection process. Besides judgment of the self, adequate perception of the task at hand is required for successful execution of the task. Healthy young adults can cope with small errors in this judgment, but for older and more fragile adults, an inadequate selection could have large consequences (e.g., causing a fall). Furthermore, ageing is accompanied by physical and cognitive decline (Spirduso, 1995; Hartshorne and Germine, 2015), a reduction in processing speed (Salthouse, 1996, 2000; Ebaid et al., 2017), and neural plasticity (Fathi et al., 2010), which could all be facets that contribute to the introduction of errors in making perceptual judgments that suit one's capability.

While falls in older adults are associated with age-related physical decline, it is suggested that accidental falls in older adults might also be associated with the misjudgment of actual physical abilities (Butler et al., 2015; Delbaere et al., 2010a). It could therefore be useful to incorporate the misjudgment in existing fall prediction models, to improve the predictive power of these models. However, to be applicable in fall prediction models, adding misjudgment (i.e., a combination of either or both an over-or underestimation of one's own motor capacities and the misperception of the environmental or task constraints) is beneficial only if this is an inherent trait and thus consistently observed across different motor tasks.

Consistency in risk-taking behaviour, which could be considered a concept analogue to misjudgment, was studied by O'Brien and Ahmed (2013, 2015). Subjects that overestimate their ability might be inclined to accept higher risk than under-estimators (Butler et al., 2015), who in turn, are more likely to bypass activities to avoid risk exposure out of fear of falling (Delbaere et al., 2004). O'Brien and Ahmed found young individuals to behave consistently as either risk-seeking or risk-averse across tasks when moving a cursor in a vertical environment as close to the edge of a cliff as possible without moving beyond the edge, either by arm movements or by whole-body leaning movements (O'Brien and Ahmed, 2013, 2015). However, since the target and the cliff were displayed on a computer screen and the target was controlled via a robotic device, an extra layer of visuomotor control was introduced. It remains unclear whether a similar consistency in the de-

gree of misjudgment holds for real-world motor tasks that require balance control, such as stepping.

Misjudgment has been directly quantified in older adults in stepping accuracy (Kluft et al., 2016) and stepping over a raised bar (Sakurai et al., 2013, 2016). Although these studies found different degrees of misjudgment in their tasks, they did not compare with other tasks, nor did they assess the construct validity of the task in question, which complicates comparison between studies.

Our overall aim was to unravel whether misjudgment is an inherent trait that transfers to other stepping tasks in young and older adults, thereby advancing this novel framework to help explain falls in older adults. To do so, we set criteria to assess the construct validity of the tasks addressing one’s (mis)judgment of physical ability. We focused on stepping ability, since stepping does initiate locomotion by moving the center of mass outside the base of support, and it is an important strategy to regain balance after a perturbation (Hof et al., 2010; Tisserand et al., 2016). Participants judged their physical abilities in four different stepping tasks; stepping over a raised bar, crossing a declining cord by stepping over it at a self-selected height, crossing a virtual river by stepping over it at a self-selected width, and making a recovery step after release from an inclined position (Fig 3.1). First the construct validity of each of the four tasks was evaluated. When tasks properly assessed physical ability as well as perceived ability, we expected correlations between both these aspects across tasks. Subsequently, we hypothesised that misjudgment is an inherent trait and therefore consistent across different stepping tasks within individuals. As older adults are more likely to misjudge their abilities because of age-related changes, we measured a group of young adults too, in order to establish the validity of the tasks. Any differences in how the perceived ability relates to the actual ability between older and young adults, is an argument against the validity of a task. After determining the validity of the tasks, we explored to what extent misjudgment is affected by ageing, by comparing the degree of misjudgment of young and older adults.

3.3 Material & methods

Participants

Fifteen healthy older adults (mean age 74, SD 5.3 and range [67-83] years, 11 females) and 9 healthy young adults (mean age 24, SD 1.5 and range [22-27] years, 5 females) participated in this study (see Table 3.1 for a detailed participant description). We excluded subjects who had any self-reported musculoskeletal or neurological disorders, major trauma in the last year, mini mental state exam-

ination score of 24 or lower, or who took medication which could have affected their gait stability. All participants could walk continuously for at least 10 minutes without any assistive walking device. The protocol was approved by the local research ethics committee (VCWE-2016-077). Participants were recruited from June to August 2016 through flyers, which were spread in popular facilities for older adults in Amsterdam, such as community centers and bridge clubs. When interested, participants were explained the aim and procedures of the experiment by telephone and an appointment was set for the measurements. The younger adults were university students who were personally contacted by one of the experimenters. Prior to the measurements, participants were again informed about the experimental procedures and signed an informed consent.

Table 3.1: Descriptive statistics of participants in both age groups. The mean values (M) and standard deviation (SD) is given for the different descriptives. Difference (t-statistics) between the two age groups are shown (*:p<0.05, **:p<0.01, ***:p<0.001)

Descriptives:				
	Young adults	Older adults	Entity	Statistic
Gender	11/4	5/4	female/male	
Age	24 ± 1.5	74 ± 5.28	years	
Weight	69 ± 13.0	74 ± 14.2	(M±SD) kg	t= 0.84
Height	171 ± 9.4	167.6 ± 8.9	(M±SD) cm	t=-0.93
MMSE	N/A	28.5 ± 1.6	(M±SD) points	
FESi	N/A	20.8 ± 5.3	(M±SD) points	
ABC	N/A	81.5 ± 16.0	(M±SD) %	
Grip strength	36.7 ± 11.4	26.3 ± 7.8	(M±SD) kg	t=-2.66*
TMT				
part A	20.6 ± 3.7	36.1 ± 12.0	(M±SD) seconds	t= 3.74***
part B	43.0 ± 19.5	82.7 ± 35.5	(M±SD) seconds	t= 3.08**
part B - part A	22.4 ± 20.4	46.6 ± 28.7	(M±SD) seconds	t= 2.21*

MMSE: mini mental state examination, FESi: Falls Efficacy Scale International, ABC: Activities-specific Balance Confidence scale, TMT: Trail Making Test, N/A: Not Available

Protocol

In the first part of the experiment, we measured grip strength (A5401 Digital Hand Grip Strength Dynamometer, Take, Niigata, Japan), trail making test (TMT, Reitan (1958)), leg length, body height, and body weight. The Falls Efficacy Scale International (FESi, Tinetti et al. (1990); Yardley et al. (2005)) and the Activities-specific Balance Scale (ABC, Powell and Myers (1995)) were also administered in the older adult group.

In the second part of the experiment, participants executed four tests (Fig

3.1) aimed at quantifying first their perceived and second their actual physical abilities. For the first task in the test battery ('bar'), we asked participants what they believed the maximum bar height would be at which they could still step over a raised bar (Fig 3.1a). A bar (2 cm x 2 cm x 137 cm) was attached to two stands using magnets, so the height of the bar was easy to adjust and a light touch caused the bar to fall. For the perceived ability on this task, the participant stood 2 metres in front of the bar stands. The experimenter slowly moved the bar either upwards or downwards in four consecutive trials, and in each trial, the participant had to say stop at their selected height. The participant was given the opportunity to adjust this height when they felt it was not at their indicated height. The mean bar height of four repetitions served as the perceived physical ability measure. For their actual ability on this task, we tested the actual reachable bar height (these procedures were adapted from Sakurai et al. (2013)). Participants started at a bar height of 5 cm, then we increased the bar height by 10 or 5 cm based on the ease with which participants could step over the bar. The bar was attached to two stands using magnets, so a light touch caused the bar to fall. When the height was reached at which the bar was knocked off we asked to try this height again. When the participants failed a second time, we lowered the bar by 2.5 cm and instructed the participants to try again. The highest successfully achieved height was recorded as the actual bar height.

For the second task ('cord'), we placed the two stands twelve meters apart and placed a string diagonally between them; at the one end, the string was raised 1.2 meters above the ground (high string stand) and at the other was at ground level (Fig 3.1b). For the perceived ability of this task, participants were standing at the starting point (next to the high string stand) and were instructed to get to the stopping point at the other side of the high string stand as quickly as possible. This task required walking to a lower part to the string, crossing the cord at the height of their own choosing, with a trade-off between the time needed for walking to a lower cord level, versus the ease with which the line could be crossed. This trade-off should drive the participants to cross the cord at about the height of their perceived maximum ability. The chosen location served as a measure of the perceived ability. For the actual ability of this task, we used the maximal bar height at the 'bar' task at which participants could step over.

In the third task ('river'), we instructed participants to walk along a virtual river, i.e., twelve meter long and tapered piece of paper, and to step across it at a location of their own choice (Fig 3.1c). Again, participants started at the widest end of the river and were instructed to walk down the river and cross it to return to the widest part of the river as quickly as possible. The position where participants

crossed was recorded and served as measure of the perceived maximum step length. The actual maximum step length was determined by stepping inside a rectangular target. In a similar fashion to the actual maximum ‘river’ height, the distance to the target was increased until participants failed to step inside the target twice.

In the final task (‘recovery’), the ability to recover from an impending forward fall by stepping was evaluated (Do et al., 1982; Karamanidis et al., 2008). Participants wore a safety harness that was secured with ropes to the ceiling. A force transducer was inserted between the ceiling and the harness, enabling fall detection based on the harness’ support. Participants were instructed to keep their body straight and their arms crossed to their chest while they leant forward, supported by a rope attached to the wall behind them (Fig 3.1d). The leaning angle (i.e., the angle between participant and the wall) was increased, and for each angle, participants indicated whether they believed they could still recover with only one step if the rope was to be released. After this procedure, the largest angle they could actually recover from was determined. The first angle was always set at 5

Figure 3.1: Visualisation of the four motor tasks. (a) Stepping over a raised bar (‘bar’). (b) Crossing a declining cord by stepping over it at a self-selected height (‘cord’). (c) Crossing a virtual river by stepping over a piece of paper at a self-selected width (‘river’). (d) Recovery from a forward fall after an unexpected release from an inclined position (‘recovery’). Leaning angle is depicted by the α .

degrees so all participants could recover themselves. Then, we increased the angle until participants could not recover, again using the same protocol as described above for the actual reachable height and actual maximum step length. Harness support above twenty percent of the participant's body weight was classified as an unsuccessful trial (Cyr and Smeesters, 2009).

Statistical analysis

First, we tested for possible differences in perceived and actual physical abilities between young and older adults, using independent samples permutation t-tests, in which p-values were adjusted using the max-statistic method (Groppe et al., 2011a). We used this permutation based approach rather than a conventional t-test with, for instance, Bonferroni adjustment, to correct for the multitude of variables that we analysed.

Next, construct validity of the tasks in the test battery was tested using the following criteria: 1) the perceived and actual physical ability measure of one task should relate highly to the same measures of another task, 2) the relation between perceived and actual physical ability should be linear.

The first criterion guarantees that the perceived and actual measures are representative of subjects' perceived and actual physical abilities; the second criterion ensures that for that task the subjects' perceived ability is indeed positively and linearly related to their actual physical ability, albeit that an offset from the identity line may exist. If subjects' perceived ability is not linearly related to their actual physical ability, it could be that they simply cannot make a valid estimate of what they can do. Ideally, perceived and actual ability would cluster around the identity line, and we have previously used the distance from the identity line as a measure of misjudgment (Kluft et al., 2016). However, offsets with respect to the identity line may exist, for instance, due to the risk involved in making errors (O'Brien and Ahmed, 2013). While this offset would not be a problem when assessing misjudgment using only one task, it may lead to problems when trying to compare misjudgment measures between different tasks, as they may have different offsets (even in different units). To examine the consistency of the actual abilities, and perceived abilities across tasks (i.e., test for the first criterion), a permutation test based on Pearson's correlation coefficient was used. To control for the family wise error rate, p-values were adjusted using the max-statistic method (Groppe et al., 2011b).

For verification of the second criterion, the linearity of the relation between the perceived and actual ability was assessed by comparing the small sample-size corrected Akaike information criteria (AIC) of a linear model with an alternative

second order quadratic model (Ton and Daffertshofer, 2016). The difference between the AIC of the linear and the alternative model (ΔAIC) was calculated by subtracting the AIC of the alternative model from the linear model ($\Delta AIC = AIC_{\text{alternative}} - AIC_{\text{linear}}$); with positive values indicating a better fit of the linear model in terms of the tradeoff between the model's complexity and accuracy. Finally, to quantify misjudgment and test for its consistency across tasks, the association between perceived and actual ability was determined using a linear regression model. To determine possible differences between the slopes of the linear fit of the two age groups, an interaction term was added to the linear regression. Any substantial differences in the regression coefficients between the age groups would affect the comparison of the degree of misjudgment between groups and between tasks. For those tasks that met the two criteria above, the degree of misjudgment was calculated. This was done by calculating the vertical distance between the perceived ability measure and the predictions of the linear regression model. The consistency of the degree of misjudgment across tasks was evaluated using a permutation test based on Pearson's correlation coefficient. Differences in the magnitude of misjudgment due to ageing were evaluated using a Levene's test for equality of variances. Instead of the common practice of using independent samples t-test for magnitudes, we evaluated variances, because the degree of misjudgment can take on a positive or negative value. In all statistical analyses, p-values below the cut-off value of 0.05 were considered significant.

3.4 Results

We excluded one participant from the 'recovery' task analysis because we could not reliably determine the smallest recovery angle, due to fear of the unexpected release. Overall, young participants had better actual abilities in all stepping tasks than older participants (Fig 3.2). Similarly, young adults perceived their abilities to be higher than their older peers, except for the perceived ability in the 'recovery' task (Fig 3.3).

Between all tasks, the actual ability measures highly correlated (Fig 3.2). For the perceived ability measures, all tasks but the 'recovery' task were highly positively correlated to all other tasks (Fig 3.3). These findings suggest that our tasks, except for the 'recovery' task, indeed measure valid constructs of perceived and actual physical ability and therefore met our first criteria. Regarding the second criteria of the construct validity, for the 'bar' ($\Delta AIC = 1.86$), 'river' ($\Delta AIC = 2.38$), and 'recovery' task ($\Delta AIC = 2.62$) the linear model appeared to better fit a quadratic alternative. However, in the 'cord' task, the alternative model was

Figure 3.2: *Distribution and correlation matrix of the actual ability measures of the different tasks. The diagonal panels (histograms) show the distribution of the three actual ability measures for the two age groups. The off-diagonal panels (scatter plots) show correlations between actual physical ability measures of different tasks. Diamonds represent young adults and circles represent older adults. Corresponding correlation coefficients and t -tests (i.e., testing the differences between young and older adults) are indicated in the top-left corner of each panel (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$). Note that the actual ability measure used for the ‘bar’ task was used for the actual ability measure for the ‘cord’ task.*

found to be the more optimal solution ($\Delta \text{AIC} = -1.98$).

All variables, except for the ‘cord’ task, appeared to meet the assumptions of normal distribution, normality of residuals, and homoscedasticity. The actual ability was predictive for the perceived ability in the ‘bar’ and ‘river’ tasks (Fig 3.4, ‘bar’: $r = 0.778$, $p < 0.001$; ‘river’: $r = 0.673$, $p = 0.002$). No significant correlation between actual and perceived ability was found for the ‘recovery’ task ($r = 0.459$, $p = 0.098$). A significant interaction effect between age group and actual ability was only found for the ‘cord’ task ($t = 4.844$, $p = 0.041$).

Regarding the consistency, the degree to which participants misjudged their

Figure 3.3: *Distribution and correlation matrix of the perceived ability measures of different tasks. The diagonal panels (histograms) show the distribution of the four perceived ability measures of both the age groups. The off-diagonal panels (scatter plots) show correlations between perceived ability measures of different tasks. Diamonds represent young adults and circles represent older adults. Corresponding correlation coefficients and t-tests (i.e., testing the differences between young and older adults) are indicated in the top-left corner of each panel (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$).*

actual ability was not significantly correlated across tasks (Fig 3.5).

Variances were equal between young and older participants for all tasks ('bar': $W = 0.925$, $p = 0.347$; 'cord': $W = 1.824$, $p = 0.191$; 'river': $W = 0.093$, $p = 0.763$; 'recovery': $W = 0.098$, $p = 0.757$).

Figure 3.4: *Perceived versus the actual ability for each of the four stepping tasks. A linear regression model was fitted to the data (dotted line). Because of the significant interaction effect with age group in the ‘cord’ task, we plotted the two different linear regression models for each age group. The identity line is indicated by the solid black line. Diamonds are representative for young adults, where circles are indicative for older adults. Participants that failed to successfully step over the string in the ‘cord’ task or step over the ‘river’ are indicated by an extra contour around the diamond or circle. The correlation coefficients are depicted in the top-left corner of each panel (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$).*

3.5 Discussion

The aim of the current study was to assess whether misjudgment transfers across stepping tasks in young and older adults. For this purpose, we proposed criteria to evaluate the construct validity of the different methods for the assessment of the degree of misjudgment. Although we found both perceived abilities as well as actual abilities highly correlated between tasks, we could not find any consistency in the degree of misjudgment between tasks. This might suggest that one’s degree of misjudgment is not an inherent trait, and should be considered as a task-dependent measure. In a study by Rhea and colleagues (Rhea et al., 2010), subjects adjusted their toe elevation after repeatedly stepping over an ob-

Figure 3.5: *Distribution and consistency matrix of the degree of misjudgment over tasks. The diagonal panels (histograms) show the distribution of the misjudgment for the two age groups, where the off-diagonal panels (scatter plots) show the correlation in the degree of misjudgment between tasks. Diamonds represent young adults and circles represent older adults. Corresponding correlation coefficients and t-tests (i.e., testing the differences between young and older adults) are indicated in the top-left corner of each panel (*: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$).*

stale, while the obstacle height was perceived similarly over time. It suggests that judgment is updated based on experience, which may make it task-specific and time variant. Yet, some nuances need to be made with respect to our findings. In contrast to previous studies with older adults (Delbaere et al., 2010a; Sakurai et al., 2013; Klufft et al., 2016), we found relatively strong associations between perceived and actual ability (Fig 3.4), implying that overall, our young and older participants were judging their physical abilities quite accurately. Some variability in the degree to which participants misjudge their abilities is required to be able to evaluate its consistency. Having relatively accurate judges in our sample led to a reduction in variance compared to other studies.

The perceived ability on the ‘recovery’ task was not correlated to perceived ability on any other task, nor was there a relationship between perceived and actual

physical ability for the ‘recovery’ task. For all other tasks, the possibility exists that the actual physical ability measure would be affected by the perceived ability, as subjects could make choices in task execution based on perceived ability. For this reason we had included the ‘recovery’ task, because we expected such choices to be limited in this task. Possibly, the ‘recovery’ task induced fear (Hsiao-Wecksler, 2008) or was too different from what occurs in (voluntary) activity in daily life, which may have complicated making an adequate judgment.

To allow making fair comparisons between tasks, we calculated the degree of misjudgment based on a linear regression model, in contrast to an identity line as described before (Kluft et al., 2016). However, using a regression model requires that the association does not differ between age groups. Only in the ‘cord’ task we found a significant interaction effect, meaning that the actual physical ability measure had a different relation with the perceived ability in young adults compared to older adults. An explanation could be that perception of risk was different between groups, where older adults were possibly reluctant to cross the line early, while young adults were more confident that they would be able to regain balance in case of an unsuccessful attempt. In support of this explanation, we see that there was no influence of age on the association of the perceived and actual ability measure in the ‘river’ task. In this task, the balance threat is minimal, since failure means stepping on a piece of paper, in contrast to the ‘cord’ task, which contained an actual balance threat.

In contrast with our expectations, misjudgment appeared not to transfer across tasks. This finding could be partly explained by the fact that for two of the four tasks (‘recovery’ and ‘cord’) we could not determine the degree of misjudgment. However, as the other two tasks (‘bar’ and ‘river’) appeared to be valid constructs, we performed an additional analysis to sort out whether other covariates possibly affected our findings. We assumed the slope of the linear regression models for each of our tasks to be similar to the identity line, yet a potential difference between slopes would imply that subjects who performed well were defined as underestimating their abilities, where the ones that performed poorly were accordingly overestimating their ability or vice versa. To check for this assumption, we therefore performed additional t-tests on the regression parameter $\hat{\beta}_1$ (i.e., testing the null hypothesis that $H_0 : \hat{\beta}_1 = 1$). The slopes of the linear regression models of ‘river’ and ‘recovery’ were significantly different from the slope of the identity line (‘river’: $t_{\hat{\beta}_1} = -3.934$, $p < 0.001$; ‘recovery’: $t_{\hat{\beta}_1} = -7.172$, $p < 0.001$). In both the ‘river’ and ‘cord’ task, the perceived ability was assessed by instructing participants to get to the other side as fast as possible, crossing the obstacle at a point which suited the participants. By doing so, participants had the freedom to walk fur-

ther, benefitting from an easier crossing at the cost of more time spent on the task. Given the slope difference, it can be argued that the benefit-cost ratio for both tasks varies from 1. This means that the benefit of walking further to decrease the width of the crossing does not equal the drawback of increasing the time spent on the task. So despite the valid construct of the ‘river’ task, the degree of misjudgment on this task could not be compared with the ‘bar’ task that did have a similar slope to the identity line.

In addition to the examination of the validation criteria, we compared the misjudgment between young and older adults. No difference between the degree of misjudgment was found, suggesting that older adults are not less accurate judging their ability than their younger peers. In contrast to our findings, Konczak and colleagues (Konczak et al., 1992) did find that young adults were less accurate in estimating their stair climbing ability than older adults, and Sakurai and colleagues (Sakurai et al., 2013) found that young adults tended to underestimate their abilities. However, neither of these studies evaluated the validity of their tasks. Our ‘cord’ task did display an interaction effect with age group, which might suggest that older adults used different strategies in indicating their perceived height than young adults. However, due to this interaction, this task no longer allowed us to validly calculate and compare the degree of misjudgment between age groups. Furthermore, our sample might have lacked the power to indicate true differences in the other (valid) tasks. We therefore cannot draw conclusions regarding the possible differences in the degree of misjudgment between age groups and need further studies with valid tasks and larger samples. Note however, that assessing between-group differences was only a secondary aim of this paper, and for the validation analysis of the tests, the subject groups were pooled giving $n=24$.

Although we were able to set and check criteria for the validity of the stepping tasks to determine misjudgment, this study had some limitations that need consideration with respect to our aim to unravel whether misjudgment is an inherent trait that transfers to other stepping tasks in young and older adults. First, three out of the four tasks we selected turned out not to be valid for examining the degree of misjudgment. Therefore, to establish a consistency of the degree of misjudgment between stepping tasks, one or more new stepping tasks need to be developed and tested based on the criteria that we have set in this paper. Furthermore, the failure rates on the cord and river tasks were not analysed. In theory, the participants that had chosen a bigger height or distance than that was measured during the actual ability trial should always have failed the trial. This was indeed the case for the ‘cord’. However, a few participants reached higher scores in the

perceived ability trial than in the actual ability trial in the ‘river’ task. This might be explained by the use of the approach velocity in stepping over the ‘river’ task, whereas they stood still before their actual maximal forward step. The validity of the ‘river’ task might be improved by giving better instructions on how to cross the river (e.g., first stand still for a moment before stepping, or walk along the river and make a 90 degrees turn before crossing the river).

3.5.1 Conclusion

The degree of misjudgment of physical ability did not transfer across different stepping tasks. However, only the ‘bar’ and ‘river’ tasks met our criteria for validly assessing the degree of misjudgment, the latter appeared not suitable for comparison across tasks. Based on the finding of the ‘bar’ task only, it remains unclear whether misjudgment of physical ability is task-specific or an inherent trait. Future research on the misjudgment of physical ability should test the construct validity of their methodology by assessing the criteria set in this study.

Chapter 4

Do older adults select appropriate motor strategies in a stepping-down paradigm?

N. Kluft, S.M. Bruijn, J.H. van Dieën, & M. Pijnappels

4.1 Abstract

Selecting motor strategies in daily life tasks requires a perception of the task requirements as well as of one's own physical abilities. Age-related cognitive and physical changes may affect these perceptions. This might entail that some older adults select inappropriate movement strategies when confronted with daily-life motor tasks, which could lead to balance loss or falls. We investigated whether older adults select motor strategies in accordance with their actual physical ability. Twenty-one older adults were subjected to a stepping down paradigm, in which full-body kinematics of selected and reactive behaviour were recorded. Stepping down from a curb can be done with either (1) a relatively low effort but more balance threatening heel landing, or (2) a more controlled but more demanding toe landing. The probability of selecting a toe landing grows with an increase in curb height. We determined the curb height at which participants switched from heel to toe landing during expected stepping down over different heights as an indicator of their perceived ability. During an unexpected step down trial, participants encountered a step down of 0.1 meter earlier than expected, because part of the walkway was removed and covered by a black cloth. We evaluated participants' actual physical ability from the reactive behaviour, with performance defined as the reduction in kinetic energy between the peak value after landing

The contents of this chapter have been published in *Frontiers in Physiology*

and the onset of the next step. To unravel whether the selected motor strategies corresponded with actual physical ability, the ability to recover from the unexpected step down was correlated to the height at which the participants switched movement strategy. The switching height was not correlated to the ability to recover from an unexpected step down ($\rho = 0.034$, $p = 0.877$). This finding suggests that older adults do not select their movement strategy in stepping down based on their actual abilities, or have an imprecise perception of their actual abilities. Future research should evaluate whether inappropriate motor strategy selection in a stepping down paradigm can explain accidental falls in older adults.

4.2 Introduction

Moving through the environment requires integration of informational cues from the environment (Gibson, 1958). Combining these cues with the perception of one's physical abilities is essential for safe movement. However, 35 percent of the older adults experience a fall at least once a year (World Health Organization, 2007). Compared to young adults – with a fall incidence of 18 percent (Talbot et al., 2005) – older adults seem either vulnerable or reckless human beings, which puts into question older adults' ability to adapt their movement behaviour to their actual physical abilities.

Appropriate perception of one's physical abilities would appear a necessity to avoid a mismatch between perceived and actual ability, but self-perception may be distorted in older adults, since even healthy ageing is accompanied with a decline in cognitive capacities (Lustig et al., 2009; Segev-Jacobovski et al., 2011). Besides this cognitive decline, a decrease in physical abilities is observed as well (Vandervoort, 2002; Woollacott and Shumway-Cook, 2002), and continuous recalibration of perceived and actual abilities appears needed (Ellmers et al., 2018).

Two studies compared the actual ability to perform tasks to judgements of one's ability to perform these tasks (Butler et al., 2015; Kluft et al., 2016). When crossing narrow planks, almost one-third of the participating older adults showed risky behaviour (Butler et al., 2015). Participants who chose a too narrow plank were more likely to fall in the upcoming year, showing the importance of such information for fall risk prediction models. In order to directly quantify the degree to which older adults misjudge their physical ability, we proposed a measure to evaluate the degree of misjudgment, and found that in most older adults perceived gait ability did not match their actual physical ability (Kluft et al., 2016). However, it is unclear whether this degree of misjudgment results in erroneous movement behaviour.

A paradigm to investigate whether movement behaviour is in alignment with movement ability, is motor strategy selection when stepping down a curb. It has been shown that there are two strategies of stepping down: a toe-landing strategy and a heel-landing strategy (Freedman and Kent, 1987; van Dieën et al., 2008; van Dieën and Pijnappels, 2009). At small curb heights, a heel landing is preferred, because toe landings are accompanied with higher effort (i.e., high ankle moment). When increasing the height of the curb, the probability of a toe landing increases, in older adults even more so than in their younger counterparts (van Dieën and Pijnappels, 2009). It has been suggested that a toe landing is preferred for higher curbs, as it allows for more controlled stepping down, since the kinetic energy generated during the step down stays within controllable limits (Buckley et al., 2008; van Dieën et al., 2008). Thus, stepping down a curb using the toe-landing strategy is thought to be safer than stepping down using a heel-landing strategy, at the cost of efficiency (i.e., higher joint moments and a loss of gait speed).

By relating the type of landing chosen to one's actual ability, we can determine whether the selected strategy is adequate. As strategy selection during anticipated stepping down entails a trade off between safety and efficiency, the actual ability measure should quantify the ability to be 'safe' (minimising balance threat) for fair comparison. This can be determined by the ability to regain balance after unexpected stepping down (van Dieën et al., 2007). Due to a sudden drop in walking surface, potential energy is quickly transformed to kinetic energy, and a large amount of kinetic energy should be dissipated to avoid balance loss (van Dieën et al., 2007). Another advantage of this paradigm is that the outcome is unlikely to be affected by one's perception of physical abilities, as there is no time for planning a motor strategy.

We aimed to investigate whether older adults select motor strategies in accordance with their actual physical ability, by comparing the selected strategy during an expected stepping down with the ability to recover from unexpected stepping down. The strategy selection during expected stepping down reflects participants' perceived ability, while kinetic energy reduction during the unexpected step reflects participants' actual ability. As we expect some individuals to select more and others to select less appropriate motor strategies, we hypothesised a moderate positive correlation between the ability to recover after an unexpected step down and the height at which subjects switched between heel landing and toe landing.

Table 4.1: *Participant descriptives. Prevalence with percentage of sample, or median values and interquartile range (IQR), the latter is indicated by the square brackets (ie., median [IQR]).*

Descriptives:			
Age	71	[7.25]	years
Females	7	(33%)	persons
Medication (≥ 4 different medicine)	3	[14%]	persons
Self-reported physical activity	1240	[309]	mins./week
Fallers (≥ 2 falls in the past year)	7	(33%)	persons
Falls in the past year	1	[1]	falls
MMSE	29	[2]	points
FESi	18	[3.25]	points
Body weight	68.7	[12.3]	kg
Body height	1.69	[0.12]	m
Grip strength	284	[96.9]	N
Max. knee-extension torque	79	[4.6]	Nm

4.3 Material & methods

Participants

Twenty-one healthy older adults participated in this study (for descriptives see table 4.1); however, due to a technical error during data collection, data of one participant were excluded from further analysis. Participants were included if they reported no neurological or muscular impairments, were able to continuously walk for 10 minutes, had a mini-mental state examination (MMSE) of 25 or higher, and did not take medication, which could affect their gait stability. This study was carried out in accordance with the recommendations of 'De Nederlandse Gedragscode Wetenschapsbeoefening', Association of Universities in the Netherlands. The protocol was approved by the 'Vaste Commissie Wetenschap en Ethiek' (# VCWE 2016-129). All participants gave written informed consent in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Protocol

Participants were asked to walk over a 7 by 1.2 meter platform, adopting the same speed as a set of light emitting diodes, which moved at a speed of 1.1 meter per second alongside the platform at eye height of the participant (Figure 4.1). Partic-

Participants were asked to step down at the edge of the platform while maintaining the indicated walking speed as much as possible. The height difference was adjustable and the participant was subjected to six different step heights (0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.10, 0.125, and 0.15 meter). A 1 by 1 meter custom-made force-plate was placed behind the height difference, so participants stepped down on top of this force-plate (Figure 4.1). The participant first executed a 0.05 m step down; the landing strategies of six trials were registered and based on the resulting strategies, the platform was either lowered or raised to a new height. We continued varying the height until a height was reached where all six step downs were heel landings (lower bound) or toe landings (higher bound), and heights between the lower and upper bound were registered.

A multinomial logistic regression was fitted to the landing strategy data, and the height at which the chance that a toe landing was used equaled the chance that a heel landing was used (i.e., $P_{\text{toe}} = P_{\text{heel}} = 50\%$) was defined as the critical height (h_{crit}).

Subsequently, for the unexpected stepping down trials, participants were again instructed to step down at the middle of the platform, but instead stepped down earlier than they expected (Figure 4.1). The height difference was kept at 0.1 meter and we informed the participants that they could experience unexpected stepping down during some of the next 15 trials. Three unexpected step downs were randomly assigned to one of these trials. The trial before the first unexpected step was considered as a normal walking condition. Behind the platform, a piece

Figure 4.1: *Illustration of the experimental set up. Participants were asked to step down at the end of the platform (landing position indicated by A). The step height was adjustable with jacks from 0.025 to 0.15 m. During the unexpected stepping down condition participants stepped down at position B, while they believed that they would step down, as instructed, at position A, with a height difference of 0.1 m. Participants were secured by a safety harness fixed with climbing ropes to the ceiling. We instructed the participant to adopt the walking speed of 1.1 m/s, as indicated by a LED strip alongside the platform.*

of black cloth spanned two bars, which were tensed by springs and kept in place by magnets, such that the cloth seemed to be walkable and part of the platform. When one of the foot markers crossed the actual height difference, it triggered the magnets to switch off, causing the cloth to quickly drop 0.1 m. This manipulation ensured a heel landing in the unexpected trials. In the other trials, the cloth covered a solid wooden platform of 0.1 m height. During all walking conditions, participants wore a safety harness attached by ropes to a railway mounted to the ceiling, to assure that the participant would not hit the floor if a fall occurred.

Data acquisition and analyses

The positions of 12 infrared light emitting clusters of three markers were captured by three camera arrays (OptoTrak, Northern Digital Inc., Ontario, Canada), to measure full-body kinematics. A kinematic model with 12 linked segments was fitted to the kinematic data, resulting in kinematic trajectories without missing data (van den Bogert et al., 2013). The segments orientations of the most distal segments of which cluster markers were not visible during data collection for less than 30 consecutive samples, were interpolated using a spherical linear interpolation (Dam et al., 1998). The total kinetic energy (i.e., rotational and translational kinetic energy of all segments) and the mechanical work of the leading-leg joints were calculated for (I) expected and (II) unexpected stepping down and for (III) normal walking conditions (the last trial prior to the unexpected stepping down). The kinetic energy during the unexpected stepping down was time normalised from the mid stance before stepping down to the leading-leg landing, and from this event again to first trailing-leg step after landing. Gait events were determined using the kinematic data and afterwards visually checked to ensure correct timing of these events. The peak in the time-normalised kinetic energy was identified and the kinetic energy reduction after the occurrence of this peak and before the trailing foot landing was determined to represent the ability to recover from an unexpected step down (see Figure 4.2 for illustration). Additionally, the body's angular momentum was calculated (reported in the supplementary material) as an alternative measure for safety in terms of balance control.

Paradigm validity

The validity of our paradigm was evaluated by examining the kinetic energy and mechanical work based on three criteria. First, we expect no difference in kinetic energy between normal walking and unexpected stepping down before the expected heel contact (i.e., the position where the participant believed they would land).

Figure 4.2: *Kinetic energy, time normalised from mid stance, via leading leg landing to trailing leg landing. The ability to recover from unexpected stepping down is defined by the area above the curve (marked by the masked area in the figure) between the peak in kinetic energy after landing and the trailing foot landing.*

Second, similar to the findings of (van Dieën et al., 2008), we expected a higher reduction in normalised kinetic energy and higher negative mechanical work done by the ankle during toe landings as compared to heel landings. Only the heel and toe landings that were observed within one step height in the expected condition were analysed for this within-subject comparison. This comparison was based on a subset of the sample ($N=18$), as two participants were very consistent in their strategy selection and did not switch strategies within any given step height. Finally, a higher kinetic energy was expected during unexpected stepping down compared to expected stepping down. Since unexpected stepping down always resulted in a heel landing, only heel-landing strategies during the expected stepping from a height of 0.1 m were selected for this comparison. It should be noted that not all participants performed a heel-landing at the 0.1 m step height, hence this comparison was made only based on a subset of the sample ($N=11$).

Statistical analysis

Statistical parametric mapping (SPM, Friston et al., 2007; Pataky et al., 2013) was used to test the three assumptions for construct validity of the paradigm. SPM two-tailed paired t-tests were used to identify differences between conditions, and resulting in the weighted magnitude of the differences (referred to as SPM(t)) for the entire time series. To test the null hypothesis, the smoothness of the time series was estimated and a threshold was calculated using Random Field Theory (Adler and Taylor, 2007) and $\alpha=5\%$, implying that 5% of random but equally smooth curves would exceed this threshold. The null hypothesis is rejected at the instances the SPM(t) value exceeds the threshold. Further technical notes about this procedure can be found elsewhere (Friston et al., 1994). SPM analyses were performed using the `spm1d` package. Next, the association between h_{crit} as the perceived stepping down ability and the actual ability to recover from an unexpected step down was evaluated using linear regression. Data analyses were performed using custom-made Matlab software (The Mathworks Inc., Natick, MA, RRID:SCR_001622).

4.4 Results

Six expected condition trials out of a total of 120 trials needed to be excluded from further kinematic analyses due to unforeseen technical errors in the kinematics.

The variability in the participants' critical height, h_{crit} , as determined by logistic regression is presented in Figure 4.3. The logistic regression was fitted using binomial data, Figure 4.4 displays the foot angle at foot contact during the step down. This data was shaped as a bimodal distribution, which confirms that stepping-down strategy selection is a binary process.

One participant performed toe landings in every trial. During normal walking, this participant performed heel landings, so we added an additional height of 0 cm and assumed that for this individual those were all heel landings, this led to an h_{crit} of 0.97 cm. The first assumption for validity assessment was met, as the test statistic (SPM(t)) did not exceed the threshold of 3.453 (see Figure 4.5), confirming that kinetic energy did not differ between unexpected stepping down and normal stepping prior to (expected) landing.

The second assumption was also met, as more kinetic energy was absorbed during toe landings compared to heel landings (see Figure 4.6). The SPM(t) exceeded the critical threshold of 3.767 ($p<0.001$) shortly before landing at the

Figure 4.3: Each participant's stepping-down behaviour, determined as the probability of a toe landing by the step height using logistic regression. The individual lines depicts the logistic fits, and the critical switching height was defined as the height at which the probability of a toe landing equaled 0.5.

lower platform (at 45% of the normalised time, or 0.08 seconds before landing), until shortly before the next step (at 93% of the normalised time, or at on average 0.70 seconds after leading leg landing). The mechanical work done by the ankle was larger after toe landing than after heel landing, as $\text{SPM}(t) > 3.389$ ($p < 0.001$) within the first 0.34 seconds after foot contact (Figure 4.7).

The third assumption that in unexpected stepping down less kinetic energy is absorbed than in expected stepping down, was also confirmed (Figure 4.8). In the first 0.2 seconds after foot contact, the test statistic $\text{SPM}(t)$ exceeds the computed threshold of 4.321. Thus, the perturbation effectively increased the kinetic energy in the system after a sudden drop in walking surface, indicating an increase in balance threat. Finally, A non-significant association ($\rho = 0.034$, $p = 0.877$) was found between h_{crit} ($M = 7.82$ cm, $SD = 3.91$ cm) and the kinetic energy absorbed ($M = 1228.84$ J·%, $SD = 568.87$ J·%) during unexpected stepping down (Figure 4.9).

Figure 4.4: Distributions of foot angles at first foot contact during stepping down. Positive angles are indicative for a plantar flexion orientation of the foot, where negative values represent a more dorsal flexion orientation.

Figure 4.5: Top panel depicts kinetic energy between mid stance and expected foot landing for normal walking and unexpected landing. For normal walking, the expected foot landing coincides with actual foot landing, while in the unexpected condition, it was the instant at which the vertical position of the leading foot crossed the platform level, where participants believed it would touch the ground at this moment in time, while actually this happened a fraction later. Bottom panel shows the $SPM(t)$ results, indicating no significant differences between the two conditions.

Figure 4.6: Top panel depicts the magnitude of the kinetic energy vector of both the heel and toe landings (\pm SD is displayed in the grey area). The SPM(t) is shown in the bottom panel, with the grey areas indicating where the difference between the two conditions was significant. The heel landing occurred at 50% of the normalised time (vertical dashed line).

Figure 4.7: Ankle joint mechanical work in the leading limb (top panel) averaged over participants during stepping down using a toe-landing strategy (red) and heel-landing strategy (blue). Error bars display \pm 1 standard deviation. The SPM(t) is shown in the bottom panel, with the grey areas indicating where the difference between the two conditions was significant. The time series were aligned on foot landing (vertical dashed line).

Figure 4.8: Kinetic energy during step down under two conditions (top panel): unexpected stepping down (red) and expected stepping down (blue). The time series of the two conditions were aligned on first foot contact on the lower platform. Note that for fair comparison of expected stepping only heel-landing strategies were considered, as only heel-landing strategies can occur in the unexpected stepping down trial. The vertical line at time 0 displays the moment of leading-foot landing, the trailing-foot landings for both conditions are indicated by the second (unexpected; red) and third (expected; blue) vertical lines. Error bars display ± 1 standard deviation. The SPM(t) is shown in the bottom panel, with the grey areas indicating where the difference between the two conditions was significant.

Figure 4.9: The critical height (h_{crit}) and the kinetic energy absorbed after unexpected stepping down displayed for each participant (circles). A best fit line was fitted to the data and the corresponding Spearman's rho and p-value are shown.

4.5 Discussion

The objective of this experiment was to evaluate whether older adults select their movement strategies in line with their physical ability. We expected a moderate positive relation between the switching height and the ability to reduce kinetic energy in (unexpected) stepping down; however, a poor and non-significant association was observed. We offer two arguments that might explain this result.

Validity of the actual ability

The weak association could be attributed to the kinetic energy measure poorly reflecting one's actual ability. In this study, we assumed that the strategy selection was made based on a trade off between safety (i.e., control of kinetic energy) and efficiency (lower joint moments and maintenance of gait speed). The data showed that, compared to toe landings, the kinetic energy remained larger after heel landing until the onset of the next step of the trailing leg. This result can be seen to confirm our assumed trade off: a too high kinetic energy would be dangerous as it may be indicative of falling, but reducing kinetic energy too much after a step down (as during the toe-landing) may be inefficient, as a certain kinetic energy is required to walk at a given speed.

Alternatively to kinetic energy as an indicator of this threat, angular momentum could possibly be more directly linked to the balance threat imposed (c.f., Pijnappels et al., 2004). However, the gain in sagittal-plane angular momentum during unexpected stepping down appeared only limited (van Dieën et al., 2007, see the supplementary material for the evaluation of angular momenta during stepping down in the present data set).

Furthermore, the unexpected perturbation was triggered when a foot marker crossed the curb position. This involved that the timing of the trigger to drop the cloth was not relative to the gait cycle, and hence differed between participants. As the planning of stepping down occurs prior to toe-off of the leading leg – the planning is barely adjusted after toe-off (Timmis et al., 2009) – it is unlikely that participants could have anticipated to the changed circumstances. In support, we did not observe adjustments in kinetic energy prior to the expected landing (Figure 4.5). Yet, analysis of the angular momentum revealed that before the instant of expected landing the momentum was altered (see supplementary material). In the unlikely situation that participants adjusted their behaviour, our actual ability measure (i.e., the height of the peak in kinetic energy) could depend on the timing of the perturbation.

It is worth noting that individuals with poor ability to recover from strong perturbations, may be able to handle small perturbations very adequately (c.f., Bruijn et al., 2013). In this study, we determined the participants' ability only once and did not continue until they failed to recover from the perturbation. Given that none of the participants fell, it can be debated how threatening the unexpected step down was. As 12% of falls in older adults occur after erroneous foot placements (e.g., an unexpected step inside a small aperture in the pavement, Berg et al., 1997), we are confident that the manipulation provoked a balance threat that could have led to falling in daily life; however, future research should confirm this.

Imprecise perception of abilities

The second proposition that could explain the weak association between the strategy selected by participants and the actual ability to recover, is that older adults generally have an imprecise perception of their actual abilities in relation to the task at hand. This is in accordance with previous studies investigating the discrepancy between the perceived and actual step ability (Kluft et al., 2016, 2017; Sakurai et al., 2013, 2016), which found that approximately one-third of older adults either over- or underestimate their abilities, when explicitly asked for their perceived ability. However, in these studies, the perceived and actual ability measures were

nevertheless significantly associated, in contrast with the present result.

Our sample consisted of a relative homogenous and fit subgroup of older adults (see Table 4.1) – enforced by the inclusion criteria – which might have hampered the association between the strategy selected by participants and the actual ability, due to a limited variability in actual abilities. Hence, these findings cannot be extrapolated to the complete population of older adults.

Another source of uncertainty is that ageing is associated with a decrease in the ankle plantar flexion torque (Judge et al., 1996). In this study the calf strength was not recorded in the current study. Toe-landing strategies rely heavily on the ability to generate ankle plantar flexion torque; an age-related decrease in the strength of the calf musculature could therefore lead to a decrease of the occurrences of toe landings. On the contrary, overall older adults prefer to step down relatively smaller step heights using toe landings compared to young adults (van Dieën and Pijnappels, 2009).

As the aim of this study was to assess the relations between physical ability and behavioural choice, we did not ask for explicit rating of the participants' perception of their ability. Therefore, we cannot rule out the possibility that the discrepancy between strategy selection and physical ability may have been caused by other factors that could affect strategy selection such as psychological factors (e.g., fear, anxiety, and self-confidence), or physiological factors (e.g., reduced visual acuity Buckley et al., 2005). To develop a full picture of the formation of motor strategy selection, future research focussing on strategy selection and psychological factors is therefore recommended.

4.5.1 Conclusions

Overall, we did not find a significant association between strategy selection and actual ability. This suggests that the older adults in our study either did not select their movement strategy for stepping down in line with their actual abilities in terms of their ability to absorb kinetic energy after unexpected stepping down, or had an imprecise perception of their actual abilities. Future research should evaluate whether this motor strategy selection is affected by psychological factors, and whether accidental falls in older adults are results of selecting inadequate strategies.

Chapter 5

The influence of a postural threat and anxiety on strategy selection during a stepping down paradigm

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5.1 Abstract

Challenging situations might affect the strategy selection during gait. We investigated how a postural threat affects movement behaviour within and between older adults by using a stepping down paradigm under low and high threat. We expected that within subjects, threat affects strategy selection when stepping down, by a shift in switching from a less demanding but more balance threatening heel landing to a more demanding yet safer toe landing at smaller step heights. This will be evident by a lower step height threshold for switching from a less demanding, but more balance threatening, heel landing to a more demanding, yet safer, toe landing in the high threat condition. Furthermore, we expected that individuals with an increased emotional response in the high threat condition would show more conservative strategy selection than their peers.

Twenty-four older adults (73.8 ± 4.9 years [M \pm SD], 14 females, 8 fallers) performed a stepping down paradigm in a low (ground level) and high (walking on a platform 0.78 m above ground) threat condition. Walking speed (1.1 m/s) was imposed by a set of light-emitting diodes along the 4 \times 0.6 m walkway. To test the effectiveness of the threat manipulation, we recorded electrodermal activity and used self-reported questionnaires to assess the perceived fear. In blocked trials,

The content of this chapter is under review (Scientific Reports)

participants repeatedly walked down step heights ranging from 0.025 to 0.15 m. We determined the height at which participants switched from heel landing to toe landing as their critical height (h_{crit}). To compare h_{crit} between threat conditions, we performed a Bayesian equivalent of a one-sided paired t -test. A Bayesian repeated-measures analysis of variance and linear regression were performed to investigate if older adults, for which the postural threat evoked an increase in the perceived fear, presented a different stepping down strategy due to the postural threat.

Physiological arousal was higher in the high-threat compared to the low-threat condition ($\text{EDA}_{\text{low}} = 16.8 \pm 10.0 \mu\text{S}$, $\text{EDA}_{\text{high}} = 18.6 \pm 8.9 \mu\text{S}$, $\text{BF}_{10} = 212.2$). Walking speed, despite being controlled, was on average 0.04 m/s slower in the high-threat condition ($\text{BF}_{10} = 4.4$). The value for h_{crit} was lower in the high-threat condition ($h_{\text{crit}} = 0.033 \pm 0.020$ m) compared to the low-threat condition ($h_{\text{crit}} = 0.043 \pm 0.018$ m; $\text{BF}_{10} = 13.7$), meaning that participants selected the toe-landing strategy more often at lower step heights. Fearful individuals did not adapt differently to the postural threat than their peers.

Our results indicate that the postural threat increased older adults' physiological arousal and changed their strategy selection in stepping down towards a more conservative toe landing at lower step heights. This suggests that, despite the additional effort, older adults prefer more cautious strategies while experiencing a postural threat. No effects of fear on strategy selection between individuals were observed, potentially due to relatively small differences in fear among participants.

5.2 Introduction

Older adults may have a perception of their physical abilities that is not in agreement with their actual physical abilities (Sakurai et al., 2013, 2016; Kluft et al., 2016). This disparity may cause selection of inappropriate motor behaviours (Horak, 2006), which might be amplified when one is exposed to a challenging situation (Kluft et al., 2018). Yet, little is known whether and how these challenging situations affect the selection of movement strategies in gait.

Standing at elevation can be challenging and such postural threat has been shown to affect the control of static motor tasks in both young and older adults (Adkin and Carpenter, 2018). This is shown through a tightened control of postural sway when standing on an elevated platform compared to standing on ground level (Carpenter et al., 2001; Adkin and Carpenter, 2018; Davis et al., 2009; Sturnieks et al., 2016). In line with the more cautious control in standing, walking at an elevation caused older adults to walk slower and adopt a more conservative

gait pattern, and these changes were more pronounced in older adults than in young adults (Brown et al., 2002; Gage et al., 2003; McKenzie and Brown, 2004; Delbaere et al., 2009). Moreover, older adults seemed to select more cautious strategies, in terms of higher toe clearance, when crossing obstacles at elevation (McKenzie and Brown, 2004). However, these studies did not constrain walking speed which might be problematic as walking slower is an effective strategy to reduce the risk of erroneous movement and may explain the observed changes in strategy selection.

To study the effect of postural threat on motor behaviour during gait in older adults, a stepping-down paradigm can be used (Kluft et al., 2018). A step down can be made using a heel landing or toe landing, with preference towards the latter as step height increases (Freedman and Kent, 1987; van Dieën and Pijnappels, 2009). Participants presumably switch from heel landing to toe landing to dissipate the kinetic energy generated by the height difference, despite the higher muscle activity associated with toe landing (van Dieën et al., 2008). As older adults can use both toe and heel landings, their strategy selection can be considered to reflect their willingness to trade-off increased effort for decreased risk. We evaluate the effect of a postural threat on strategy selection between and within older adults by using an elevation manipulation as described previously in studies on standing.

We hypothesised that a postural threat during stepping down shifts the step height at which individuals switch from heel to toe landing to lower values. We predicted that participants will be more cautious in stepping down in a high threat environment, resulting in kinematic adaptations reflecting such cautious behaviour: an increase in leading leg ankle plantar-flexion prior to landing, and an increase in leading leg knee flexion and ankle dorsiflexion angular velocity after landing (van Dieën et al., 2008).

Furthermore, with a postural threat, the consequence of falling due to balance loss increases. Therefore, a postural threat can evoke emotional responses such as fear and anxiety (Adkin and Carpenter, 2018). Davis et al. (2009) examined the association between height-related changes in balance control and fear in young adults. They found that fearful individuals at high threat leaned farther away from the platform edge and their centre of pressure featured larger amplitudes and higher frequencies than in less fearful peers. Hence, during a gait task, older adults with higher perceived fear might respond even stronger to a stepping down task (i.e., by switching to a toe landing at smaller step heights) than their less fearful peers. Therefore, our second aim was to explore the between-subject difference in perceived fear and how this relates to a change in stepping down strategy selection. We expected fearful older adults to be less adaptive than their less fearful peers. A better understanding of how a postural threat and fear affect movement strategy

selection (between and within individuals) may help explain why some older adults fall while others with similar physical capacity do not.

This study is confirmatory and we pre-registered our hypotheses and research methods online (AsPredicted.org); which is available on the Open Science Framework repository at (<https://osf.io/fpzea/>).

Figure 5.1: *Experimental set-up of the postural threat condition. Participants were instructed to walk over a $4\text{m} \times 0.6\text{m}$ walkway at an imposed walking speed indicated by LEDs that ran parallel to the walkway. Participants stepped down a height difference that was constructed in the middle of the walkway, and which was adjustable to multiple step heights (ranging from 2.5 to 15 cm). The walkway was secured by a small railing around the edge of the platform that assured foot placements within the platform boundaries. The low threat condition deviated solely from the high threat condition in terms of the height of the walkway (at floor level). Participants wore a safety harness during both experimental conditions.*

5.3 Material & protocol

Participants. Older adults (aged 65 years and older) were recruited by word of mouth and we asked employees in residential homes, gyms, and other recreational facilities for seniors to spread advertisement posters. Potential participants were excluded from participation in this study if they had a mini-mental state examination score of 23 or lower, reported any neurological, musculoskeletal, or anxiety disorders, had uncorrectable visual impairment, suffered from a serious injury during the last 9 months, could only walk with a walking aid, were unable to walk independently for 10 consecutive minutes, or took medication which could affect gait stability.

Efficacy, falls, and strength. Before the experiment, the participant's fall concern was assessed, using the Falls Efficacy Scale International (FESi, Yardley et al. (2005)). The self-reported number of falls in the last 6 months was recorded, and we administered the modified Gait Efficacy Scale (mGES, Newell et al. (2012); Goldberg et al. (2016)). For both hands, handgrip strength was determined in three assessments (Reijnierse et al., 2017) using a dynamometer (A5401-Digital Hand Grip Strength Dynamometer, Take, Niigata, Japan). Participants stood with their arms straight and parallel to their trunk, and the dynamometer was adjusted to fit their hand. To promote maximal effort, verbal encouragement was provided while participants squeezed the dynamometer (Reijnierse et al., 2017). The mean of the maximum value (from three attempts) recorded from each hand was used to determine the handgrip strength (Reijnierse et al., 2017).

Stepping-down task. Participants were asked to walk barefoot over a 2 by 0.6-m platform, stepping down on top of a second 2 by 0.6-m platform (Figure 6.1). In all trials, participants wore a safety harness. Walking speed was guided by a set of light-emitting diodes (LED) moving at a speed of 1.1 m per second alongside the platforms, and we instructed the participants to maintain a constant walking speed matching the LED speed. Participants were instructed to continue walking after stepping down, towards a highlighted area taped on the walking surface at the same speed. Then, we switched the position of the two platforms so the participant did not have to return to the starting position for the next trial. The step-height difference was adjustable and participants confronted up to six different step heights (0.025, 0.050, 0.075, 0.100, 0.125, and 0.150 m). The first evaluated step height was at 0.05 m. Participants performed six stepping-down trials per step height, after which this step height was changed, according to a protocol described

previously (Kluft et al., 2018). The selected landing strategies (i.e., toe or heel landing) for each trial, within the range of step heights at which six heel landings and six toe landings occurred, was categorised by the experimenter. This complete stepping-down procedure was performed at ground level (i.e., low threat condition) and elevated 0.78 meters above floor level (i.e., high threat condition). The order of the low- and high-threat conditions was randomised across participants. Prior to the protocol, participants completed an extensive set of familiarisation trials at ground level to minimise potential learning effects.

Perceived fear. We monitored the fear of falling related to each step-height block of six trials using a short questionnaire. This was assessed using a visual analog rating scale ranging from 0% to 100%. The participants, for whom the ratings of perceived fear after the first block of six trials increased with threat condition, were classified as being fearful (i.e., fear group: $\Delta\text{fear} > 0$).

Physiological arousal. Physiological arousal was assessed (Zaback et al., 2015) by recording electrodermal activity (EDA). Surface electrodes were placed at the base of the palm using common electrode adhesive and a hypoallergenic conducting gel. All areas immediately under the electrodes were cleaned to improve conductivity. The analog EDA signals were sampled at 1000 samples per second. The average of the EDA was determined and expressed in μS . The difference in EDA (ΔEDA) between conditions (i.e., high-low) was computed and used for further analysis.

Kinematics. A total of 7 LED infrared cluster markers was used to measure the movement of body segments and placed on the skin at the feet, calves, thighs, and pelvis. Two camera arrays (Optotrak, Northern Digital Inc., Waterloo, Ontario) were used to capture the 3D position of the cluster markers and sampled with a rate of 100 samples per second. Anatomical landmarks were identified and digitised using a pointer (Zatsiorsky, 2002).

Data analysis

A psychometric curve was fitted to the individual's landing strategy data, the height at which both strategies were equally likely to occur was defined as the critical switching height (h_{crit}) (Kluft et al., 2018). In the unlikely situation that all evaluated heights resulted in either toe or heel landings, h_{crit} was respectively set to 0.015 or 0.165 m.

A 3-D linked segment model was fitted to the kinematic data (Kingma et al., 1996), and gait events were detected automatically (Hreljac and Marshall, 2000), and visually verified afterward. Time series between the heel strike preceding the step-down, until the heel strike of the step following the step down were analysed. Missing data were interpolated using spherical linear interpolation (Dam et al., 1998; Kluft, 2019) thereby predicting segmental orientation, and when a complete cluster marker was not visible, one of the cluster markers was interpolated using a spline function.

Outcome measures were calculated from the resulting trajectories: (I) step length was determined by the distance between the feet during the double support phase in the forward direction, and (II) knee and ankle joint angles and angular velocities were calculated by a decomposition of the relative rotation matrices and their derivatives using Euler angles. Joint angles and angular velocities were time-normalised to the gait cycle.

Furthermore, investigation of the motor strategy requires constraining walking speed, as this could affect strategy selection (van Dieën and Pijnappels, 2009). To validate our experimental paradigm, the participant’s walking speed was calculated as the mean of the derivative of the pelvis marker trajectory in the progression direction, which should not statistically differ between threat conditions.

Sampling plan and statistical analysis

A Bayesian approach was used to test our alternative hypothesis that h_{crit} decreases in the high-threat condition, compared to the null hypothesis that there is no difference between the high- and low-threat conditions. To test this hypothesis, we used a Bayesian equivalent of a one-sided paired t -test, with a weakly informed prior distribution (i.e., a Cauchy distribution with an interquartile range of $r = 1$ centred around an effect size of 0 (Wagenmakers et al., 2018)). We used a one-sided test, as a decrease in h_{crit} with an increase in threat level was expected. We monitored the Bayes factor during data collection until a threshold of meaningful evidence was reached (Edwards et al., 1963; Rouder, 2014; Schönbrodt et al., 2017; Wagenmakers, 2007). We set this threshold to a Bayes factor (BF_{10}) of 10, as this is generally considered as being ‘strong’ evidence in favour of H_1 (or similarly a BF_{10} of 0.1 in favour of H_0). First, twenty healthy older adults (age 65-85 years) were included, and this sample was extended until the BF_{10} exceeded the selected threshold, or a maximum of fifty participants was reached. In comparison with a frequentist approach, with a sample size of $n = 50$ subjects, an effect size of Cohen’s $\delta = 0.4$ can be acquired with an 85% statistical power and a 5% Type I

error rate.

To test whether older adults that reported an increased fear responded differently from their non-fearful peers, participants were categorised in groups, based on whether the postural threat affected their perceived fear of falling (fear group). A Bayesian repeated-measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) with threat-group interaction was used to evaluate whether fearful older adults respond differently to elevated walking – in terms of the strategy selection (h_{crit}) – than their less concerned peers. For this analysis, JASP (JASP Team, 2018) default priors were used ($r = .5$ for the fixed effects = 0.5 and $r = 1$ for the random effects) and Bayes factors were reported.

A Bayesian linear regression was performed to explore whether the change in physiological arousal (ΔEDA) and the strategy selection in the low threat condition ($h_{\text{crit}}[\text{low}]$) could explain the h_{crit} in the high threat condition ($h_{\text{crit}}[\text{high}]$). For this analysis a default Jeffreys-Zellner-Siow prior with scaling factor 0.354 was used (JASP Team, 2018).

To evaluate the effectiveness of the postural threat and thus the validity of our manipulation, measures of perceived fear, physiological arousal, and walking speed at 0.05 m step height were compared between threat conditions using Bayesian paired t -tests with one-sided Cauchy distributed priors (interquartile range $r = 1$, centred around an effect size of 0). We assumed our protocol to be effective when it increased the perceived fear and physiological arousal, and walking speed did not statistically differ under different threat conditions.

Finally, Bayesian statistical parametric testing (SPM, Friston et al. (2007); Pataky et al. (2013); Serrien et al. (2019)) was used to identify the kinematic differences between threat conditions. To ensure that our findings did not mainly rely on the selected priors we assessed the robustness of the Bayes factor for all Bayesian tests (Wagenmakers et al., 2015, 2018) (these results are reported in the OSF repository). Non-parametric alternatives were used, if the assumptions of a statistical test were violated, hence a Bayesian signed-rank test (van Doorn et al., 2017) was applied for the tests that compared fear, anxiety, and walking speed across threat conditions. The Bayesian parametric hypothesis testing was performed in JASP (JASP Team, 2018), and the SPM analysis (code adapted from <https://osf.io/q5b72/>, Serrien et al. (2019)) and the non-parametric tests (code adapted from <https://osf.io/gny35/>, van Doorn et al. (2017)) were performed in R (R Core Team, 2018).

Deviations from the preregistration document

Two aspects that deviate from the registered document should be noted. First, we planned to determine the slope of the psychometric curve at h_{crit} to reflect the consistency of the strategy selection. In contrast to earlier studies (Kluft et al., 2018, 2019), we found an overall lower critical height in the present study. This led to a shift of the psychometric curve towards zero, which makes the slope of the curve less reliable as there were fewer data available to fit the lower end of the curve (due to the inability to evaluate stepping down at negative step heights). Hence, we omitted the consistency of strategy selection from further analysis.

Second, for the handling of missing data, visual evaluation of the interpolated data demonstrated that the resulting trajectories were adequate, and there was no need to continue fitting linked-segment models, as suggested in the preregistered document.

5.4 Results

Twenty-four healthy older adults were measured (see Table 6.1 for participants' descriptives). Walking in the high-threat condition increased physiological arousal (mean low = $16.8 \pm 10.0 \mu\text{S}$, mean high = $18.6 \pm 8.9\mu\text{S}$, Cohen's $\delta = 0.85$, and $\text{BF}_{10} = 212.2$). Perceived fear was marginally affected by threat condition (median low = 1 IQR 1 point, median high = 1 IQR 0.5 point, and $\text{BF}_{10} = 0.7$). Walking speed was slightly lower than indicated by the set of LEDs in the high-threat condition (mean low = $1.08 \pm 0.13 \text{ m/s}$, mean high = $1.04 \pm 0.14 \text{ m/s}$, Cohen's $\delta = -0.49$, and $\text{BF}_{10} = 4.6$). When exposed to the high-threat condition, participants lowered h_{crit} (mean h_{crit} low = $0.043 \pm 0.018 \text{ m}$, mean h_{crit} high = $0.033 \pm 0.020 \text{ m}$, Cohen's $\delta = -0.59$ with 95%CI [-1.03, -0.19], and $\text{BF}_{10} = 13.7$). Figure 5.2 presents h_{crit} under low and high-threat conditions and the probability density distributions of the effect size δ . Furthermore, step length during the step down was slightly longer in the high-threat condition compared to the low-threat condition (mean low = $0.54 \pm 0.06 \text{ m}$, mean high = $0.57 \pm 0.06 \text{ m}$, Cohen's $\delta = 0.59$, $\text{BF}_{10} = 5.0$). However, this finding was probably due to the change in landing strategy, resulting in relatively more toe landings, as this effect did not remain when only heel landings were compared (mean low = $0.58 \pm 0.06 \text{ m}$, mean high = $0.57 \pm 0.06 \text{ m}$, Cohen's $\delta = -0.15$, $\text{BF}_{10} = 0.3$). Note that this analysis with heel-landing strategies was only possible for a subset of participants ($n = 13$), which selected heel landings in both conditions at comparable step heights. Normalised ankle joint and knee joint angles and velocities are depicted in Figures

Table 5.1: *Participant descriptives, response, and explanatory variables. When the variable was normally distributed the mean with standard deviation $M(SD)$ was reported, otherwise, the median with interquartile range $Mdn[IQR]$ was reported. Solely for count data, the number and percentage $n(\%)$ of the total sample size was reported.*

<i>Descriptive variables (N = 24 older adults)</i>				
Age	73.8	(4.9)	M(SD)	years
Females	14	(58.3%)	n(%)	persons
Fallers	8	(33.3%)	n(%)	persons
Fall history	0	[1]	Mdn[IQR]	falls
MMSE	29	[1]	Mdn[IQR]	points
Body weight	66	[26.7]	Mdn[IQR]	kg
Body height	1.66	(0.1)	M(SD)	m
Grip strength	23.7	[12.6]	Mdn[IQR]	kg
FESi	19	[6.5]	Mdn[IQR]	points
mGES	97.5	[7.5]	Mdn[IQR]	points
	<i>Low threat</i>	<i>High threat</i>	<i>(High-Low)</i>	
<i>Within variables</i>	M \pm SD	M \pm SD	Cohen's δ	BF ₁₀
Physiological arousal [μ S]	16.8 \pm 10.0	18.6 \pm 8.9	0.85	212.2
h_{crit} [m]	0.043 \pm 0.018	0.033 \pm 0.020	-0.59	13.7
Walking speed [m/s]	1.07 \pm 0.13	1.03 \pm 0.14	-0.48	4.4
Step length* [m]	0.58 \pm 0.06	0.57 \pm 0.06	-0.16	0.3
	Mdn [IQR]	Mdn [IQR]		BF ₁₀
Perceived fear [points]	1[0]	1[0.5]		0.7

* *Considering only stepping downs that considered heel landing strategies.*

5.3 and 5.4. The SPM analyses of the kinematics showed that joint angles did not differ between conditions. However, the leading leg's ankle angular velocity was altered in large parts of the gait cycle while stepping down under high threat.

For the between-subject comparison, we found in seven participants the postural threat affected their self-reported fear. Repeated measures Bayesian ANOVA revealed that the (threat \times group) interaction effect model was not preferred over the main effect models (fear group model: $\eta_p^2 < 0.001$, BF₁₀ = 0.41). Hence, the data are uninformative and provide no evidence that could support our hypothesis that fearful individuals would or would not respond differently – in terms of h_{crit} – on threat condition than their peers. Note, that despite the between-group sample size differences, the ANOVA's assumptions were not violated.

The Δ EDA term in the Bayesian linear regression did not improve the fit of the model ($R^2 = 0.45$, BF₁₀ = 0.33). Hence, the change in physiological arousal

Figure 5.2: A) Probability density distributions of effect size of h_{crit} between low and high threat conditions. The one-sided prior distribution is indicated by the dashed line. The posterior distribution, indicated by the solid line, equals the prior distribution updated by our observed data. The posterior density distribution indicates the likelihood of certain effect size (Cohen's δ) on the horizontal axis. The 95% credible interval (95%CI) is indicated by the horizontal bar. Given the BF_{10} , the alternative hypothesis that h_{crit} differs with threat condition is 13.7 more likely than the null hypothesis that there is no difference between condition. B) Violin plots of h_{crit} , with jittered individual data points superimposed. Figures adjusted from JASP, jasp-stats.org.

did not explain differences in h_{crit} between the low and high-threat conditions.

5.5 Discussion

This study aimed to understand how a postural threat, induced by a height manipulation, affects movement strategy selection in older adults. The validity of our threat manipulation was assessed by evaluation of the perceived fear, physiological arousal, and walking speed. The increase in EDA suggests the manipulation imposed a postural threat and provoked a physiological arousal response (Adkin and Carpenter, 2018). However, the ratings of the perceived fear, were unaffected by the imposed threat, suggesting that the elevation in the high threat condition was not sufficient to induce a significant change in the perceived fear.

Despite the imposed walking speed, the postural threat drove participants to walk slightly slower compared to walking at ground level. Multiple studies that did not constrain gait speed have shown a larger effect of postural threat on walking speed (Brown et al., 2002; Gage et al., 2003; McKenzie and Brown, 2004; Delbaere et al., 2009). A previous study on strategy selection during stepping down showed

Figure 5.3: A) Ankle joint angle averaged over participants during stepping down under high (red) and low (blue) threat conditions. The shaded area displays ± 1 standard deviation. Time series are normalised from the heel strike before stepping down to the step after stepping down, and up to the next heel strike. B) Ankle joint angular velocity averaged over participants during stepping down under high (red) and low (blue) threat conditions.

that the strategy selection is a function of walking speed (van Dieën and Pijnappels, 2009). As walking speed differed between threat conditions, this may have affected switching heights. However, the observed difference in walking speed was relatively small (<0.05 m/s), implying that the magnitude of this difference is not sufficient to explain changes in stepping-down strategy.

Our results confirmed our initial hypothesis that older adults adjusted their stepping-down behaviour when under threatening conditions. This is in line with our expectation that postural threat causes older adults to behave more cautiously, and therefore switch to toe landings at lower heights. Changing stepping-down behaviour under threat may contribute to an increased sense of safety, and may be protective in daily-life situations, despite the increased effort in terms of muscle

Figure 5.4: A) *Knee joint angle averaged over participants during stepping down under high (red) and low (blue) threat conditions. The shaded area displays ± 1 standard deviation. Time series are normalised from the heel strike before stepping down to the step after stepping down, and up to the next heel strike.* B) *Knee joint angular velocity averaged over participants during stepping down under high (red) and low (blue) threat condition.*

force production (van Dieën et al., 2008). The increased arousal that our participants experienced at elevation may replicate that experienced by individuals who suffer from a fear of falling during daily-life activities. This could imply that older adults with high concern of falling may select less efficient movement strategies during daily-life tasks.

Previous work on stepping-down behaviour suggested that strategies are selected based on a trade-off between safety and efficiency (van Dieën and Pijnappels, 2009; Kluft et al., 2017). This study adds evidence for this trade-off as older adults preferred the safer strategy when walking on elevation. Between individuals, we found no evidence for an interaction effect of threat with perceived fear on the change in strategy selection of stepping down across threat conditions. The absence of such an interaction effect might be due to the threat of our experimental manipulation; the variability on the self-reported perceived fear was only

marginal, which might be due to our modest platform elevation of 0.78 m. For comparison, Davis and colleagues (Davis et al., 2009) evaluated standing at heights of 0.8 m, 1.6 m and 3.2 m and found robust fear responses only at the 3.2 m height. Even though walking is more challenging than standing at an elevated height, it is recommended for future research to study gait at higher elevations (>0.78 m) to distinguish how different psychological conditions contribute to altered strategy selection in older adults.

The small effect sizes of the ANOVA's threat \times group interaction and linear regression suggest that the postural threat does not alter the stepping-down strategy of the more aroused or fearful older adult relative to their peers. In this study, we assumed that the strategy selection is the variable through which the safety during stepping down is controlled. This seems to be an acceptable assumption, given that the postural threat decreased h_{crit} . So, why is the strategy selection not different between our fear groups? Instead of our initial hypothesis that a postural threat would drive fearful older adults to switch to a toe landing at smaller step heights, fear might affect the consistency of stepping-down strategy. Hence, following this explanation, we would expect a larger variance in strategy selections in the individuals susceptible to fear. This would lead to a less consistent strategy selection, rather than an altered h_{crit} , reflected by a less steep slope of the psychometric curve. Unfortunately, we had to omit the measure of consistency of strategy selection, as we were not able to quantify the slope of the psychometric curve with sufficient precision. Hence, future research should incorporate more step heights near the height of h_{crit} to provide for a higher resolution, allowing valid quantification of the consistency of the strategy selection.

Our experiment differed from previous studies (cf., Brown et al. (2002); Delbaere et al. (2009)) in three major aspects: 1) we imposed walking speed using a LED strip, 2) we used a stepping down paradigm, and 3) our participants wore a safety harness during all walking conditions. As we imposed the walking speed, differences in walking speed between conditions were minor. No differences in step length between conditions were observed; therefore, we believe that the previously reported differences in step length can be (mainly) explained by the change in walking speed over conditions.

We evaluated the knee and ankle joint kinematics to detect differences in control between threat conditions within either toe landing or heel landing strategies. The mechanical challenge of stepping down is to keep control of the angular momentum and kinetic energy induced by the height difference (van Dieën et al., 2008; Kluft et al., 2018). Even though some participants still selected heel-landing strategies when walking under high threat, the threat-related adjustment could have been

governed by adaptations, reflected in different kinematic trajectories. However, we did not observe any difference in the joint kinematics between heel landings across conditions. Another effective strategy is to adjust the foot placement to increase the step length (van Dieën et al., 2007). We had expected the step length to increase with the postural threat to allow more reduction of angular momentum at landing; however, our data do not provide the evidence to support this hypothesis. These findings confirm that older adults adjusted to the postural threat by making a discrete switch in stepping-down strategy.

This study had some limitations to be considered. In this experiment, participants walked barefoot, which most likely reduced the probability of stepping down with a heel-landing strategy. Indeed, we observed lower h_{crit} (Kluft et al., 2018, 2019), compared to earlier work on stepping-down strategies in which participants wore footwear. Moreover, our participants were required to be able to walk for at least 10 consecutive minutes independently. This may have caused a selection bias as solely fit older adults (mean grip strength = 23.7) with a low fear of falling experienced during daily life activities were recruited (median FES-i = 19, Delbaere et al. (2010b) established cutoffs of 16-19 for low concern and 20-27 for moderate concern). These individuals may have been less susceptible to the postural threat as they have higher confidence in their gait ability.

5.5.1 Conclusion

In accordance with the initial and preregistered hypothesis, our findings indicate that older adults change their motor behaviour, in terms of strategy selection in a stepping-down paradigm, due to a postural threat imposed by walking at elevation. Despite the additional effort of the selected landing strategy, older adults adjusted their motor strategy selection in response to the imposed threat towards using a toe landing.

Chapter 6

Does misjudgment in a stepping down paradigm predict falls in an older population?

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6.1 Abstract

Although measures of actual and perceived physical ability appear to predict falls in older adults, a disparity between these two, also known as misjudgment, may even better explain why some older adults fall, while their peers with similar abilities do not. Therefore, we investigated whether adding a misjudgment term improved prediction of future falls. Besides conventional measures of actual (physical measures) and perceived abilities (questionnaires), we used a stepping down paradigm to quantify behavioural misjudgment. In a sample of 55 older adults (mean age 74.5 (SD = 6.6) years, 33 females, and 20 fallers over a 10 month follow-up period), we tested the added value of a misjudgment term and of a stepping-down task by comparing experimental Bayesian logistic-regression models to a default null model, which was composed of the conventional measures: Falls Efficacy Scale international and QuickScreen. Our results showed that the default null model fitted the data most accurately; however, the accuracy of all models was low (area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC) ≤ 0.65). This indicates that neither a misjudgment term based on conventional measures, nor on behavioural measures improved the prediction of future falls in older adults (Bayes Factor₁₀ ≤ 0.5).

The contents of this chapter have been published in Royal Society of Open Science

6.2 Introduction

Manoeuvring safely through the environment requires the ability to perceive the biomechanical requirements of an encountered task, and the ability to judge whether these requirements lie within one's physical ability. This entails that safe behaviour depends not only on an accurate perception of the task at hand, but also on a precise perception of one's physical ability (Kluft et al., 2017). An error in either of these perceptions could lead to misjudgment, by either over- or underestimation, which may result in sub-optimal movement strategy selection. As ageing is accompanied by a decline in cognitive and physical abilities, inaccurate judgment may become more apparent at an older age. One consequence of our ageing society is the increase of falls and fall-related injuries (Talbot et al., 2005; Verma et al., 2016; Timsina et al., 2017), which may (partly) be explained by such misjudgments (Sakurai et al., 2013).

Many of the existing models predicting falls in older adults already incorporate either a measure of actual ability or a measure of perceived ability. For instance, the Timed Up and Go test (Podsiadlo and Richardson, 1991), Berg balance scale (Berg et al., 1992), Physiological Profile Assessment (Lord et al., 2003), or QuickScreen (Tiedemann et al., 2010) are all attempts to predict falls by assessing the physical state of the older individual. On the other hand, the gait- and falls-efficacy scales (McAuley et al., 1997; Yardley et al., 2005) are measures that assess the individual's confidence to do certain activities, which closely resembles one's perceived ability. However, although previously suggested by Weijer et al. (2019), a misjudgment term by means of an interaction between the perceived and actual ability has not yet been incorporated in fall prediction models.

Misjudgment between older adults' perceived and actual ability has been studied in stair climbing (Konczak et al., 1992), stepping over obstacles (Sakurai et al., 2013, 2016; Kluft et al., 2017), balance and reaching ability (Robinovitch and Cronin, 1999; Sugihara et al., 2006), and gait (Butler et al., 2015; Kluft et al., 2016). Although each of these tasks requires adequate balance control, the use of these tasks for determining misjudgment may be hampered by two concerns. First, the perceived ability measure is commonly determined by asking participants explicitly for their maximum ability, which could promote socially desirable responses (Furnham, 1986). Second, the perceived ability was measured in a static posture and lack of optic flow might hamper the perception of task requirements (Gibson, 1958; Rhea et al., 2010).

Recently, attempts have been made to resolve these concerns. Butler and co-workers measured the perceived ability more implicitly by designing a dynamic

task in which healthy older participants were exposed to a walking track with six different walkways varying in levels of difficulty (Butler et al., 2015). These levels were presented so that the easiest option was presented farthest away. Participants were instructed to complete the track as fast as possible, thereby selecting the walkway that they believed would be optimal in terms of both safety and efficiency. However, participants were not allowed to actually walk across the walking track, and the misjudgment was determined by predicting their performance on the selected track on the basis of the gait characteristics during another walking bout. Interestingly, they found that overestimation was associated with a higher incidence of future falls. Similarly, Kluft and co-workers created a tapered paper “river”, which participants needed to cross as quickly as possible, inducing a trade-off between efficiency (i.e., be as quick as possible) and safety (i.e., choosing a crossing point that lies within one’s stepping ability) (Kluft et al., 2017). Instead of relating the outcome measures to falls, the objective was to investigate whether a similar degree of misjudgment was observed between multiple stepping tasks involving explicit and implicit estimates of self-perceived ability. In both studies, the instructions were to perform the task as fast as possible. However, as walking speed changes the biomechanical requirement of the task at hand, the selected walking speed should be incorporated in the judgment people make, and should therefore be considered when assessing misjudgment in dynamic gait tasks.

We propose a paradigm that alleviates these concerns, namely stepping down to a lower level, while maintaining a constant walking speed. When stepping down, humans select a strategy and perform either a heel or a toe landing (Freedman and Kent, 1987; Kluft et al., 2018). The latter strategy is considered to be the “more stable but more [physically] demanding” strategy (van Dieën and Pijnappels, 2009, pp.345), and is commonly selected with larger height differences. Compared to a toe landing, a heel landing is considered to be less physically demanding, but balance control becomes more challenging, as less kinetic energy is absorbed in landing at the lower level (van Dieën et al., 2008; Kluft et al., 2018). A distinct height at which an individual switches the preferred strategy, the critical switching height (h_{crit}) appeared highly variable between participants (van Dieën and Pijnappels, 2009; Kluft et al., 2018). This behavioural measure h_{crit} can be regarded as a measure of perceived ability, but does not rely on any instructions regarding the strategy selection. Another advantage of the stepping-down paradigm, is that participants are less aware of the strategy selection they make during this task. Moreover, the judgment is dynamic as the participants are moving towards the height difference.

In this study, we used the stepping-down paradigm to obtain a behavioural mea-

sure of misjudgment. To estimate misjudgment, we need to relate one's perceived ability to one's actual physical ability (see Kluft et al. (2018) for a direct comparison). For the current study, we defined the actual physical ability as a composite score of the stepping performance on two stepping tasks. The first stepping task quantified the participant's maximal step length (Kluft et al., 2017), whereas the second task quantified the participant's ability to step over an obstacle (Sakurai et al., 2013).

Our main objectives are to understand 1) whether adding a misjudgment term can help to predict fall risk, and 2) whether these behavioural measures improve the identification of prospective fallers compared to conventional physical and cognitive measures. We predict that overestimation is associated with prospective falls, and thus a combination of high perceived and low actual ability should be associated with higher fall incidence. Hence, an interaction between perceived ability (i.e., h_{crit}) and actual ability, as suggested by Weijer et al. (2019), would improve the power to predict fall risk compared to a model based on merely physical and falls efficacy measures.

6.3 Material & methods

Participants

Sixty-two older adults (age ≥ 65 years, median age 73.5 [IQR 10] years, 37 females, 20 fallers) participated in the study. Participants were included when they had a mini-mental state examination score above 18 points (i.e., no to mild cognitive decline, excluding severe cognitive impairment), were able to walk 20 meters continuously without becoming short of breath, experiencing dizziness, or perceiving pain in - or pressure on the chest. The complete experimental procedure was explained prior to any experimentation, and all participants provided written consent. This study was part of a larger longitudinal study on self-perception, gait quality, and physical activity (Veilig In Beweging Blijven, Weijer et al. (2019)). The Vrije Universiteit's ethics committee (i.e., Vaste Commissie Wetenschap en Ethiek) approved all experimental procedures (# VCWE 2016-147).

Protocol

Participants were invited for the assessment once at the Vrije Universiteit. After the assessment, they were asked to keep a fall diary during a follow-up period of 10 months.

Falls

Falls were monitored for 10 months using fall diaries and monthly telephone calls to ask about the occurrence of falls over the previous month. The baseline measurement was scheduled in the first month that falls were monitored. A fall was defined as “inadvertently coming to rest on the ground, floor or other lower level, excluding intentional change in position to rest on furniture, wall or other objects” (World Health Organization, 2007, pp.1). Participants were classified as fallers when 1 or more falls were recorded. A total of 55 out of 61 participants completed the entire follow-up.

Assessments

Actual physical ability (composite score)

During the assessment, participants performed a set of motor tasks from which a composite physical ability score (x_{act}) was calculated. This composite score was calculated on the basis of a larger dataset from a cohort study of our group (Weijer et al., 2019), and consisted of a weighted average of the participant’s maximal step length (Step length) and maximum performance to step over (Step over) an obstacle. The weights in the equation (see eq. 6.1) were determined by the first principal component, which explained 90% of the variance.

$$x_{act} = 0.405967 \cdot \left(\frac{Step\ over}{Leg\ length} \right) + 0.91389 \cdot \left(\frac{Step\ length}{Leg\ length} \right) \quad (6.1)$$

Perceived ability (stepping-down protocol)

Two equally sized platforms (1.2 x 2 m) were placed in front of each other (Figure 6.1). Six stair-like wooden blocks supported one of the platforms at variable heights. The height difference between the platforms could be adjusted between 2.5 to 15 cm, in steps of 2.5 cm. At the far end of the second platform, a 28.5 by 46.5 cm target was fixed on the surface of the platform. Parallel to the two platforms, a light emitting diode (LED) strip, with 30 LEDs per meter, was placed at eye height. A small beam of 20 consecutive LEDs moved along the light strip at a speed of 1.1 m/s.

Participants were instructed to walk from the starting point of the first platform towards the end point on the second platform, thereby stepping down at the height difference, while walking at the same speed as the moving LEDs. Upon arrival at the target, participants stood still for a moment and returned to the starting

Figure 6.1: *Illustration of the experimental set up. Participants were asked to step down at the end of the first platform. The step height was adjustable and ranged from 0.025 to 0.15 m. The participant was instructed to adopt a walking speed of 1.1 m/s, as indicated by a LED strip alongside the platform.*

point. The initial height difference was 5 cm. For each height difference, the procedure was repeated six times. Based on the strategy selection during these six repetitions, the next height was determined using a fixed protocol (described in Klufft et al. (2018)). In brief, if one of the six repetitions resulted in a heel landing, the height difference was increased by 5 cm. We continued this approach of increases in height differences, until all 6 repetitions at a given height were toe landings, or the maximum height of 15 cm was reached. Finally, the height difference was set at a level of 2.5 cm higher than the height at which only heel landings occurred. This fixed protocol ensured that all heights between the height at which only toe-landings and the height at which only heel-landings occurred were observed, within a reasonable timeframe.

Data collection and analysis

During the assessment, the stepping-down strategies of the participant were classified based on visual inspection, to adjust the height difference between the platforms using the protocol described above. However, for objective analyses of the strategies, all trials were captured using two video cameras and were categorised post-hoc by two independent pairs of raters. Conflicting categorisations were rated once more by the first author.

A nominal logistic regression model was fitted to the landing-strategy data of

each participant. This resulted in a sigmoid model that described the landing strategy as a function of height difference. The height at which the probability of a toe landing (P_{toe}) equaled the probability of a heel landing (P_{heel}) was defined as h_{crit} (Kluft et al., 2018) normalised to participant’s leg length.

Statistical procedures

The inter-rater agreement of the categorised stepping-down strategies was determined by assessing Krippendorff’s alpha ($K\alpha$) (see Hayes and Krippendorff (2007) for a discussion on reliability measures). A $K\alpha$ near one indicates excellent reliability, while a value of zero is indicative for no reliability, and a negative $K\alpha$ indicates a systematic disagreement.

To discriminate the people who fell from those who did not fall in the following months, four Bayesian logistic regression models were constructed (eq. 6.2, 6.3, 6.4, 6.5), including actual physical ability (x_{act}) and perceived ability (i.e., h_{crit}). Bayesian inferences enhance the interpretation of the model, as posterior distributions of the model parameters can be computed, thereby incorporating the uncertainty in the parameters. Moreover, the evidence in favour of a model can be quantified by deploying Bayes factors (BF), which facilitates comparisons of models. Experimental models (eq. 6.2, 6.3, 6.4, 6.5) were compared to a default null model, based on two input variables commonly accepted in fall prediction and indicative for actual and perceived fall risk: (i) the QuickScreen (QS, Tiedemann et al. (2010)) and (ii) the Dutch version of the falls-efficacy scale international (FESi, Yardley et al. (2005); Kempen et al. (2007)), respectively. The probability of a fall (P_{null}) as a function of the FESi and QS in the first model is given by the equation:

$$P_{\text{null}}(\text{FESi}, \text{QS}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{FESi} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{QS})}}. \quad (6.2)$$

Here and in the rest of the manuscript, the β_i are predictor coefficients that are obtained by fitting the logistic regression to the prospective fall data. The QuickScreen identifies risk factors by assessing balance, gait, strength, and endurance to examine lower-limb function, and a composite score of the risk factors is associated with falls (Tiedemann et al., 2010). The FESi, a self-report questionnaire, examines one’s concern about falling in a variety of gait-related daily activities (Yardley et al., 2005), and can reliably distinguish between fallers and non-fallers (Delbaere et al., 2010b).

First model

The first experimental model contained an updated version of the null model. Delbaere et al. (2010a) showed that the discrepancy between older adults' perceived and physiological fall risk can help to explain falls. This discrepancy in fall risk is implemented by adding an interaction term (i.e., $FESi \times QuickScreen$) to the null model. Although this model incorporates a misjudgment term, the term is not directly linked to participants' actual movement behaviour. In the first experimental model, the probability of a fall (P_1) as a function of the FESi and the QS is given by the equation:

$$P_1(FESi, QS) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot FESi + \beta_2 \cdot QS + \beta_3 \cdot FESi \times QS)}} . \quad (6.3)$$

Second model

The second experimental model (eq. 6.4) contained the x_{act} and the height chosen for switching at the stepping down paradigm (h_{crit}). In the second experimental model, the probability of a fall (P_2) as a function of x_{act} and h_{crit} is computed by the equation:

$$P_2(x_{act}, h_{crit}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot x_{act} + \beta_2 \cdot h_{crit})}} . \quad (6.4)$$

This model incorporated participants' physical ability and perceived ability, represented by the x_{act} and the h_{crit} terms respectively. Although this model contained information about the physical and the perceived ability, it lacks a misjudgment term.

Third model

The next model incorporated the misjudgment term. Since the misjudgment can be treated as a weighted form of the perceived ability (h_{crit}), it should be related to one's actual physical ability (x_{act}). As the first model, the third experimental model (eq. 6.5) was extended with an interaction of the x_{act} and h_{crit} variables. The probability of a fall (P_3) in the third model is given by the equation:

$$P_3(x_{act}, h_{crit}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot x_{act} + \beta_2 \cdot h_{crit} + \beta_3 \cdot x_{act} \times h_{crit})}} , \quad (6.5)$$

in which the interaction $x_{act} \times h_{crit}$ represents the misjudgment term.

Input variables and priors

For all models, each input variable was standardised, and weakly informative priors were assigned to all model predictors (Gelman, 2008). The prior for the model's intercept followed a zero centred Cauchy distribution with scale 10, and a zero centred Cauchy distribution with scale 2.5 was selected for the predictor coefficients priors, thereby following the recommendations of Gelman et al. (2008). Collinearity of the predictors was assessed using the variance inflation factor (VIF), and showed that there was no severe collinearity that would have affected the analysis ($VIF < 1.9$). Hence, correlations between predictors were low ($r_{(\text{Quickscreen}, \text{FESi})} = 0.06$; $r_{(\text{x}_{\text{act}}, \text{b}_{\text{crit}})} = 0.20$).

Model outcome measures

For each of our experimental models, the median of the β_i coefficient posterior distribution and the corresponding 95% highest density interval (95%HDI, Bayesian analogue to the 95% confidence interval) were calculated. Subsequently, we computed the leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO; Vehtari et al. (2017)), quantifying the model's out-of-sample prediction accuracy, and the Watanabe-Akaike Information Criterion (WAIC, Watanabe (2010)), which is a Bayesian equivalent of the Akaike Information Criterion. Then, each experimental model was compared with the null model, and the evidence in favour of the experimental model relative to the null model was quantified using Bayes factors (Vandekerckhove et al., 2015). Analyses were performed using custom-made software in Matlab R2018a, and all Bayesian analyses were performed using the 'brms' package (Bürkner, 2017) in R (R Core Team, 2018).

6.4 Results

Participant descriptives

Data of one participant were excluded because this participant was unable to complete the stepping-down protocol. Furthermore, 6 participants did not complete the 10 months follow-up. Twenty (36.4%) of the remaining 55 older participants were considered fallers (falls ≥ 1 , see Table 6.1 for participant descriptives).

Strategy rating agreement

The two independent pairs of raters disagreed on only six stepping-down strategies (0.6% of all trials), suggesting a very high inter-rater reliability, which was

Table 6.1: *Participant descriptives, response and explanatory variables. When the variable was normally distributed the mean M with standard deviation (SD) were reported, otherwise the median Mdn with interquartile range [IQR] were reported. Solely for count data the number and percentage $n(\%)$ of the total sample size were reported.*

<i>Descriptive variables</i>	(n= 55 older adults)			
Age	74.5	[6.6]	M(SD)	years
Females	33	(60%)	n(%)	persons
Unique medication	2	[4]	Mdn[IQR]	units/week
Falls in the past	1	[1.5]	Mdn[IQR]	falls
MMSE	28	[2.5]	Mdn[IQR]	points
Body weight	74.3	[12.3]	M(SD)	kg
Body height	168.9	(8.8)	M(SD)	cm
Grip strength	27.5	[7.4]	Mdn[IQR]	kg
Max. knee extension moment	7.4	[3.2]	Mdn[IQR]	Nm
<i>Response variable</i>				
Fallers*	20	(36.4%)	n(%)	persons
<i>Explanatory variables</i>				
FESi	20	[5]	Mdn[IQR]	points
QuickScreen (QS)	4	[2]	Mdn[IQR]	risk factors
x_{act}	1.23	(0.21)	M(SD)	(arbitrary variable)
h_{crit}	7.1	[5.7]	Mdn[IQR]	cm

* Considered a faller when 1 or more falls occurred.

confirmed by the high Krippendorff's alpha value ($K\alpha=0.99$). The six conflicting trials were classified once more by one of the authors. On average participants switched strategies (h_{crit}) at a height of 8.0 cm (SD=4.8 cm).

Fall prediction models and contribution of misjudgment

The models coefficients and their statistics are presented in Table 6.2. The QuickScreen's 95%HDI in the null and first model excluded zero, even as the intercept in all models. However, for all other coefficients, the 95%HDI spanned zero. The misjudgment terms – the interaction term in the first ($FESi \times QuickScreen$) and third ($x_{act} \times h_{crit}$) model – did not contribute to explaining the data, with coefficient estimates (i.e., median of the posterior parameter distribution) of $\beta_{FESi \times QuickScreen} = 0.73$ and $\beta_{x_{act} \times h_{crit}} = -2.26$, and the Bayes factor for these predictors reaching a value of $BF_{10} = 0.44$ and $BF_{10} = 2.12$ respectively.

The values for the goodness of fit of the models are displayed in Table 6.3. Both

6.4. RESULTS

Table 6.2: *Posterior summaries of logistic regression coefficients. The median, the standard error, the lower and upper boundary of the 95% highest density interval (95%HDI), and the Bayes factor BF_{10} of the coefficient's posterior distribution are depicted in this table.*

Model	Eq.	Coefficient	Median	std. error	95%HDI		BF_{10}
					Lower	Upper	
<i>null model</i>	[6.2]	Intercept	-0.60	0.29	[-1.24	-0.04]	0.20
		<i>FESi</i>	0.35	0.53	[-0.77	1.43]	0.22
		<i>QuickScreen</i>	1.02	0.61	[-0.17	2.22]	0.84
<i>1st model</i>	[6.3]	Intercept	-0.63	0.30	[-1.21	-0.06]	0.23
		<i>FESi</i>	0.42	0.56	[-0.81	1.60]	0.24
		<i>QuickScreen</i>	1.03	0.59	[-0.19	2.27]	0.86
		<i>FESi</i> \times <i>QuickScreen</i>	0.73	1.22	[-1.70	3.39]	0.44
<i>2nd model</i>	[6.4]	Intercept	-0.56	0.29	[-1.12	0.00]	0.15
		x_{act}	0.03	0.55	[-1.14	1.13]	0.31
		h_{crit}	0.24	0.56	[-0.78	1.39]	0.18
<i>3rd model</i>	[6.5]	Intercept	-0.49	0.30	[-1.05	0.13]	0.09
		x_{act}	0.23	0.63	[-1.04	1.44]	0.21
		h_{crit}	0.25	0.61	[-0.99	1.43]	0.21
		$x_{act} \times h_{crit}$	-2.26	1.35	[-5.23	0.31]	2.12

measures of the goodness of fit (i.e., LOO and WAIC) favoured the null model, as the lowest values were found for this model. However, the coefficients' BF_{10} were lower than 1 (see BF_{10} s of null model in Table 6.2), indicating that FESi and QuickScreen only increased the model's complexity, while their contribution was limited. The BF_{10} values for the experimental models (see BF_{10} s for model 1,2, and 3 in Table 6.3) containing our stepping-down measures were lower than 1, showing that the data support the null model over the other experimental models.

Exploratory analysis 1

To gain more insights into our results regarding the interaction, we categorised the participants in four groups based on the actual physical ability and the perceived ability (switching height), and QuickScreen and FESi. Figures 6.2A and 6.2B show fall incidence over 10 months for each of the subgroups. The group divisions were made on the basis of 1) a mean split of x_{act} and h_{crit} and 2) a mean split of QuickScreen and FESi. According to this analysis, most participants aligned their movement behaviour with the actual ability measure. The fall incidence on the basis of behavioural measures was highest in the high perceived ability and low

actual ability group (fall incidence = 55%), and lowest in the group that had a relative low-perceived and low-actual ability (fall incidence = 31%). In comparison, the fall incidence on the basis of the conventional measures was highest in the poor QuickScreen and poor FESi group (fall incidence = 56%), whereas no one fell in the good QuickScreen and good FESi group (fall incidence = 0%).

Exploratory analysis 2

To better understand and compare the predictive value of the different models, we computed the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curvature for each model (see Figure 6.3). In the ROC curves, the sensitivity (i.e., the proportion of actual positives that are correctly identified) is plotted as a function of the specificity (i.e., the proportion of actual negatives that are correctly identified) for different criterion values (i.e., cut-points) of the model. The area under the ROC curvatures (ROC_{auc}) is a measure of how accurate the model can distinguish between fallers and non-fallers. In our sample, the combined model of FESi and QuickScreen reached an accuracy of .63 (null model ROC_{auc}). The addition of the $FESi \times QuickScreen$ interaction did not increase the model's accuracy (1st model $ROC_{auc} = .65$). The models containing the behavioural measures did not perform better than the conventional measures (2nd model $ROC_{auc} = .57$, and 3rd model $ROC_{auc} = .62$).

6.5 Discussion

The present study was designed to investigate the use of a stepping-down task as an objective measure of misjudgment and investigated whether adding a misjudgment term can improve fall prediction models. None of the experimental models

Table 6.3: *Goodness of fit measures. The measures reported here: the leave-one-out cross validation (LOO), Watanabe-Akaike Information Criterion (WAIC), and the Bayes factor (BF_{10} ; the evidence of the experimental model relative to the null model). In general, for model comparisons, the smaller the LOO or the WAIC the better the model fits the data.*

Model	Input variables	Eq. [†]	LOO	WAIC	BF_{10}
<i>null model</i>	$(FESi, QS)$	[6.2]	74.52	74.45	
<i>1st model</i>	$(\bar{F}ESi, \bar{Q}S, \bar{F}ESi \times \bar{Q}S)$	[6.3]	76.14	75.89	0.44
<i>2nd model</i>	(x_{act}, h_{crit})	[6.4]	77.40	77.33	0.27
<i>3rd model</i>	$(x_{act}, h_{crit}, x_{act} \times h_{crit})$	[6.5]	75.39	75.17	0.58

[†] Reference to equation.

Figure 6.2: The percentage of fallers in four subgroups of the data. **A)** Groups were separated on the basis of a mean split of the two input variables $FESi$ and QuickScreen (QS). **B)** The groups were separated on the basis of a mean split of the two input variables x_{act} and h_{crit} . The numbers of participants within a group is given by n .

performed better than the null model that contained solely a clinical measure and questionnaire (i.e., $FESi$ and QuickScreen). Adding a misjudgment term to the null model did not improve the predictive quality of the model (e.g., *null model's* $LOO = 74.52$, versus *1st model's* $LOO = 76.14$). Moreover, we found that the addition of a misjudgment term, led to only a very minor improvement in prediction of prospective falls when expressed as the interaction between perceived and actual ability of behavioural measures (i.e., $x_{act} \times h_{crit}$) (e.g., *3rd model's* $LOO = 75.39$, versus *2nd model's* $LOO = 77.40$).

The misjudgment predictor (i.e., $\beta_{x_{act} \times h_{crit}}$) estimate was negative, suggesting that participants were less likely to have fallen in the next months when the actual ability corresponded with the perceived ability. Previous studies showed that particularly overestimation of one's ability was associated with fall risk (Sakurai et al., 2013; Butler et al., 2015). However, we found that a model containing the misjudgment predictor was only 2.12 times more likely than a model containing solely h_{crit} and x_{act} , meaning that the data were indecisive in supporting one model above the other (i.e., $BF_{10} = 2.12$). Hence, we can conclude that if there is an association of misjudgment with falls, this association is weak.

Conventional clinical fall prediction models provide only poor to fair predictive ability (Gates et al., 2008; Scott et al., 2007; Lee et al., 2013). Our null model comprised two of those conventional measures: the QuickScreen and the

Figure 6.3: Receiver operating characteristic curves for the individual models: sensitivity (the proportion of actual positives that are correctly identified), and specificity (the proportion of actual negatives that are correctly identified), are depicted for different criterion values of the model. The area under the ROC curve (ROC_{auc}) is given as a measure of the overall accuracy of the model, a larger ROC_{auc} indicates better performance of the model to distinguish between fallers and non-fallers. The diagonal line (with an ROC_{auc} of 0.5) represents a non-discriminatory model.

FESi. Both measures have demonstrated reasonable accuracy, in terms of the area under the receiver operator curve (ROC_{auc}), to predict falls (QuickScreen $ROC_{auc} = .72$ Tiedemann et al. (2010); FESi $ROC_{auc} = .67$ Delbaere et al. (2010b)). However, we found a lower accuracy ($ROC_{auc} = .63$) after combining these measures, while our sample was comparable with previous reports (c.f., Delbaere et al. (2010b); Tiedemann et al. (2010)). To illustrate this, our sample consisted of older individuals with levels of concern about falling of 22.3 ± 5.3 points on the FESi (ranging from a score of 16-43), which is somewhat low in comparison with a sample mean of 28 in a Dutch population (Kempen et al., 2007), but well within the range that was reported to be associated with prospective falls (e.g., mean of 22.1 ± 6.4 in Delbaere et al. (2010a)). Moreover, the median number of risk factors

identified by the QuickScreen in our sample was 4, which was higher than what was identified in an external validation study (risk factors = 3 Tiedemann (2006)). Furthermore, it should be noted that the QuickScreen tool's ROC_{auc} values were developed in a larger cohort and on the basis of multiple falls data. Recurrent fallers are likely to suffer from more chronic impairments in either perceived or actual ability. Only 14 participants in our study fell more than once during follow up, which was a too small number to distinguish recurrent fallers from occasional fallers and non-fallers.

In this study, we computed the misjudgment by relating h_{crit} to the composite score x_{act} . These measures were used to reflect the participant's perceived and actual physical ability, but the measures are not directly related as they are assessed with separate tasks (c.f., Sakurai et al. (2013); Kluft et al. (2016, 2017)). Measures that are more directly related would give a better indication of when a person truly exceeds his or her actual physical ability. In an earlier approach to quantify the misjudgment we determined the actual physical ability during unexpected stepping down. The reactive behaviour that was provoked by the unexpected stepping down was quantified, and the ability to absorb kinetic energy reflected the actual physical ability. Hence, this gives a more direct quantification of the misjudgment. However, this approach can only be applied in fit older adults and would not be feasible in frailer older adults. To our knowledge, there is no test available that directly links the perceived and actual physical ability, without priming or biasing the participant on his/her behaviour.

Participant's perceived ability was assessed using a stepping-down paradigm. The strength of such a paradigm is that the perceived ability is not explicitly assessed. However, the stepping-down behaviour might have been affected by the participant's anthropometry. For instance, limited dorsiflexion range-of-motion could induce toe-off earlier in the gait cycle, which may affect one's stability. This physical limitation may drive participants to select a toe-landing strategy where a heel landing would have been more appropriate. Hence, we recommend to take passive/active ankle range of motion into account in future research that implements a stepping-down paradigm

We investigated whether misjudgment in an experimental setting was associated with higher fall risk in daily life. Therefore, we assumed that the movement selection in daily life can be derived by assessing movement selection in an experimental setting. The transfer of the misjudgment between several (explicit) stepping tasks seems to be weak (Kluft et al., 2017), which suggests that the misjudgment is highly tasks specific. Yet, how the misjudgment measure relates to daily life movement selection, has not been studied yet. Furthermore, we assumed

that an inappropriate strategy selection in daily life would lead to falls. However, a fall is a manifestation of an impaired system, a system that – even if impaired – has a very low error rate (a fall rarely occurs). Although falls were recorded prospectively over 10 months, the number of falls might not be a perfect measure to quantify the impairment of a system in daily life.

In this study, a Bayesian statistical analysis was performed, in contrast to the conventional frequentist statistics as generally used in falls prediction. Accidental falls in older adults form a noisy measure, and the effect sizes are often small and unlikely to be known prior to the execution of the study. A meaningful power analysis is therefore hard to perform at the start of an experiment. Unlike conventional frequentist statistics, in a Bayesian framework, one can perform a study in which samples are added until a certain level of evidence has been reached without making inferential errors (Rouder, 2014). As falls in older adults are generally monitored on a yearly basis by medical bodies, studies performing statistics in a Bayesian framework can improve the accuracy of the model parameters by incorporating information of the preceding year. Therefore, it is advisable to consider performing Bayesian statistical analysis in fall-related research.

6.5.1 Conclusion

Our findings showed that a misjudgment term does not improve the prediction of future falls in older adults, be it an interaction term between conventional measures or between behavioural measures of perceived and actual physical ability.

Chapter 7

Synthesis

Humans are challenged constantly while manoeuvring in complex environments. However, our understanding of the art of selecting adequate movements is limited, as we lack theories that can describe how adequate movements are selected. In this thesis, we studied whether and how the perceived ability and strategy selection is in accordance with one's physical ability. Hereby, we introduced a theoretical framework that could explain how adequate movements are selected.

7.1 Summary

The theoretical framework of this thesis was introduced in **chapter 1**. This framework can help understand how the interplay between perceived ability and actual ability has an effect on the probability of successful movement execution. The adequacy of a movement depends on the integration and quality of the perception of one's physical ability and of the task requirements. The main objective of this thesis was to understand how adequate movements are selected by assessing the interplay between the perceived ability and actual ability. We focussed on older adults, as discrepancies between the perceived ability and the actual physical ability have been observed for a substantial set in an older population (Delbaere et al., 2010a; Sakurai et al., 2013) and the consequences of selecting an inadequate movement due to such misalignment can be more harmful.

In a first study to understand the underlying mechanisms of producing adequate movement behaviour in older adults, a method to measure the degree of misjudgment was proposed in **chapter 2**. In this chapter, the association between the perceived and actual gait ability was quantified directly using a virtual walking path. We instructed the participant to walk on a treadmill, while we evaluated the perceived and actual gait ability using a step-width and a walking-speed paradigm.

In the step-width paradigm, we instructed participants to rate their gait ability by indicating the smallest path-width for which they believed they could walk, without stepping outside the path's boundaries. In the walking-speed paradigm, participants were instructed to walk at the highest speed they believed they could still walk, without stepping outside the path's boundaries. We computed the path width and walking speed for which 90% of all steps would be placed within the path's boundaries. The validity of both paradigms was tested. Results showed that a path-width paradigm can validly quantify the degree of misjudgment. In this path-width paradigm, the participants were instructed to estimate the smallest path width they believed they could walk on, without stepping outside the borders of the path. This was compared with their actual ability, which was determined by assessing the stepping accuracy. Evaluation of the degree of misjudgment within this paradigm revealed that the association between the perceived and actual ability was weak (Spearman's $\rho = 0.31$), which suggested that older adults experienced difficulties judging their gait ability. Although the path-width paradigm can validly determine the degree of misjudgment, the assessment relies on heavy instrumentation and is time-consuming. Therefore, we introduced other stepping tasks that might be used to assess the degree of misjudgment in the next chapter.

Our next objective was to understand whether misjudgment transferred to other daily-life tasks. If one has an inaccurate perception of his/her physical abilities this should be apparent in a range of movements, and as such, the misjudgment should transfer across tasks. Hence, **chapter 3** describes the consistency of the degree of misjudgment across different stepping tasks in 9 young and 15 older adults. Moreover, a set of criteria was proposed that can be used to evaluate the validity of a misjudgment task/measure. The results of this experiment showed that the degree of misjudgment was not very consistent across different stepping tasks (max. $r = 0.42$), even though the perceived and actual ability measures correlated strongly ($r > 0.67$) in all valid stepping tasks. This suggested that our sample could accurately judge their abilities, but it can be questioned whether this also results in adequate movement selection. In chapters 2 and 3, a direct link between the perceived and actual ability was assumed, and the behavioural choice was neglected in these paradigms. The following chapters focus on the behavioural choice, which supposedly emerges from the perceived ability and the perceived task requirements.

In **chapter 4**, we studied the behavioural choice in 21 older adults and its alignment to their actual ability. To this end, we used a stepping-down task in which the stepping down behaviour was quantified by means of the critical

switching height between optional heel and toe landing strategies. This critical height resembled one's behavioural choice, which was determined during expected stepping down and assumed to reflect one's perceived ability. Participant's actual ability was determined during unexpected stepping down, in which they stepped down earlier than expected. The reactive behaviour that was provoked by this unexpected stepping down (quantified as the ability to absorb kinetic energy), reflected the actual ability. The results of this experiment suggested that older adults do not select their movement strategy on the basis of their actual ability. This conclusion was deduced from the result that the critical switching height did not associate with kinetic-energy absorption during unexpected stepping down (Spearman's $\rho = 0.03$).

The aim of **chapter 5** was to investigate whether context affects adequate movement selection and how potential task consequences alter the behavioural choice. This was studied in 24 older adults by observing how a postural threat changed stepping-down behaviour. The postural threat was induced by a height manipulation, which showed to be an effective manipulator to induce changes in physiological arousal. A more conservative stepping-down behaviour was selected as a consequence of the postural threat (i.e., the critical height decreased under threat). This result is of importance as it indicates that the strategy selection is a controlled variable, that is deliberately adjusted to fit the perceived needs of the environment. Furthermore, in the same chapter, we examined whether older adults who showed an increased fear at elevation would be less adaptive than their peers that did not show an increased fear response. The participants were split into fear groups, and their stepping-down behaviour in high- and low-threat conditions was compared. Results suggested that the between-group differences in how participant adjusted their stepping-down behaviour to our postural threat, were negligible, probably due to the relatively low induced fear levels.

In the final study, described in **chapter 6**, we investigated whether a behavioural misjudgment is predictive of the probability of success in daily life. Our theoretical framework dictates that a poor judgment of one's actual ability could lead to inadequate movement selection, and therefore a lower probability of success. As such, falls in older adults seems to be a product of inadequate selected movements. Hence, we investigated in 55 older adults whether a misjudgement term could improve fall prediction models. We registered falls in a ten months follow-up and compared the predictive power of the behavioural model over conventional models either with or without the addition of misjudgment. Three experimental models were compared to a default model containing the conventional measures: FESi (Yardley et al., 2005) and QuickScreen (Tiedemann et al., 2010). In the first

experimental model, we extended the default model with a misjudgment term, that is the interaction between FESi and QuickScreen. The second and third models consisted of behavioural measures, which were determined by the participant's stepping-down strategy selection (i.e., h_{crit}) and the actual stepping ability (i.e., x_{act}) on two different stepping tasks. Again, the latter model was extended with an interaction term, between h_{crit} and x_{act} , that represented the behavioural misjudgment. Our findings showed that the experimental models containing information about the misjudgment did not outperform any model without this information. Moreover, none of the investigated models could accurately predict prospective falls ($\text{ROC}_{\text{auc}} \leq 0.64$). This indicated that a misjudgment term that consisted of neither behavioural measures nor conventional measures improved the prediction of prospective falls.

7.2 General discussion

In the previous sections, I summarised the main results and conclusions of the individual chapters. Each of these studies contributed to our understanding of how adequate movements are selected, but also resulted in subsequent questions and points of discussion when combining them in the framework as presented in chapter 1 (Figure 1.1). Hence, in the following sections, I will discuss our finding within the context of this framework on how to select adequate movements. I will highlight gaps that may be left, critically evaluate the conflicting results within and between our experimental chapters and provide scientific and clinical implications of the work presented in the thesis.

7.2.1 Perceiving the task requirements

When a novel motor task is encountered, humans rely mainly on the available visual information to estimate the task requirements for selecting a movement strategy. In relation to ageing, adequate perception of the task requirement is of primary importance to select adequate movements, as reduced visual function (Klein et al., 2003), and loss of visual field (Freeman et al., 2007) are associated with falls.

In this thesis, we left the mechanisms of how the perception of the task requirements is formed untouched. In studies on goal-setting and performance research, task complexity is commonly used as an important determinant, which is closely related to the task requirements but entails more mental processing tasks over longer time-scales. Previous research has shown that perceived task complexity might deviate from actual task complexity (Campbell, 1988; Maynard and Hakel,

1997). Moreover, perceived task complexity predicts task performance better than the actual objective task complexity (Gerhardt and Luzadis, 2009). Hence, further investigation is required to understand how task requirements are perceived, and whether the knowledge of task complexity can be applied to our framework’s task requirements and to learn about its effect on the probability of success.

7.2.2 Aligning the perceived & actual ability

An important result from this thesis is that most older adults can give an accurate estimation of their actual abilities in multiple stepping tasks (Figure 3.4). This suggests that humans form representations of their physical abilities, which may be used to plan future movements. These representations are convenient (when accurate), as this allows for swift judgments about which movement strategy to select. On the basis of such a representation, we can select the most optimal strategy for a given task.

However, when we focussed on gait tasks, older adults experienced difficulties aligning the perceived and actual gait ability (Figure 2.2a). This difference between chapter 2 and chapter 3 could not be explained by differences in the study populations between chapters, because similar selection criteria were used, and indeed, the population showed similar characteristics (i.e., age, gender, FESi, handgrip strength, fall history, MMSE). A more likely explanation for the difference between chapter 2 and chapter 3 is that the level of complexity differed between gait and stepping tasks. To illustrate this, in the gait task of chapter 2, we instructed the participant to estimate their smallest path width. This entailed that participants should be able to simulate their performance to predict what their smallest path width would be, which can be considered a complex task in itself. In contrast, in the stepping tasks of chapter 3, participants possibly used some reference anthropometric to relate the task to (e.g., relating step height or distance to a physical entity such as leg length), which makes the task somewhat less complex. A similar argument has been used to describe findings in a functional reach task, in which young adults estimated their arm length (i.e., anthropometric measure) more precise than their postural limits (i.e., ability measure) (Robinovitch and Cronin, 1999). As the smallest walkable path width relies on one’s physical ability, it might, therefore, be more complex to estimate than step height or step length. As producing an adequate movement partly depends on the perceived ability, it involves the accurate perception of both aspects: the anthropometric dimensions and the physical ability. Daily-life tasks, such as obstacle avoidance or ascending stairs, may rely more on one aspect than on the other. However, the performance on measures that relate strongly to fall risk, such as gait stabil-

ity (van Schooten et al., 2015) or postural sway (Zhou et al., 2017), are typically dictated by one’s physical ability, and not by the individual’s anthropometrics. Therefore, for the assessment of the probability of success, we would recommend incorporating a measure of the participant’s actual ability on a gait ability tasks similar to the task assessed in chapter 2.

7.2.3 From a perceived ability to a movement choice

After integrating the perceived ability and the perceived task requirements, a movement choice should be selected according to these perceptions. If the movement choice comes forth from these perceptions, then the perceived ability measure should (partially) correlate to the movement choice. As we studied the movement choice in this thesis by recordings of the strategy selection during a stepping-down task (chapters 4-6), these choices were expected to be (to some degree) associated with the individual’s perceived ability.

This association could be inspected using the dataset from chapter 6, as this dataset was part of a larger cohort study on self-perception in older adults (Weijer et al., 2019). This allowed us to compare how measures of one’s perceived ability, assessed in different tasks, associated with one’s movement choice (i.e., critical height (h_{crit}) in the stepping down task). Figure 7.1 shows the resulting association, and indicates that the perceived ability measures do not associate well with the strategy selection in a stepping-down task.

Why does the perceived ability not associate with the strategy selection during a stepping-down task? One simple and apparent argument could be that safety during stepping-down is not achieved by switching to a toe landing. However, our results in chapter 5 indicate that the critical height of switching from heel to toe landings is a function of postural threat, suggesting that safety can be acquired through the differentiation of movement strategies. A more likely argument is that other facets vary between subjects and across tasks. For instance, chapter 4-5 examined the strategy selection in a stepping-down task. The strategy selection might be co-determined by the perceived comfort, as recent studies suggested that young subjects adjusted their movement pattern to gain more comfort (i.e., smaller impact forces), even though these adjustments demanded higher metabolic costs (Zelik and Kuo, 2012; Skinner et al., 2015).

7.2.4 Updates from past behaviour

The probability of successfully executing a movement task is to a large extent determined by the knowledge we have available before task execution (Körding and

Wolpert, 2004). The quality of the *a priori* information relies on the adequacy of internal (i.e., perceived ability) and external (i.e., task requirement) models. These models are updated and improved after each repetition (Narain et al., 2014), resulting in higher judgment accuracy (Franchak et al., 2010).

Improvements of the accuracy may only occur when the *online* perception of the probability of success is adequate, which is not always evident. A recent study on the perceived postural sway during a balance task in young adults showed that this performance perception was modulated by a postural threat (Cleworth and Carpenter, 2016), implying a context-dependency of the perceived performance. It is still unclear how the perceived performance affects the perceived ability and therefore future behaviour. On the one hand, imprecise updates could make anxious older individuals more likely to select inadequate movements, but on the other hand, might be protective as it may push them towards more safe behaviour.

Rhea et al. (2010) investigated how an illusion affects toe clearance over repe-

Figure 7.1: Perceived ability measures at multiple tasks versus the critical switching height. None of the perceived ability measures associated with the critical switching height.

titions in obstacle crossing. They showed that, despite the fact that the overestimated perception of the obstacle height remained unchanged, young participants reduced their toe clearance over repetitions. The authors argued that conscious visual perception is not a necessity for motor adaptations in obstacle crossing. However, since there was no interaction between the obstacle and the participant in this experiment, there are no other sources available that inform the participant on the height of the obstacle aside the visual perception. Hence, we believe that it is not the *a priori* visual perception, but rather the *online* visual perception that provided the information that led to the change in toe clearance. Nonetheless, in our studies, the strategy selection might also have been affected by (sub)conscious perception of the success of stepping down in previous trials at the same step height, as we recorded the landing strategy numerous times over a range of step height. Therefore, future research should illuminate whether strategy selection is subjected to trial-to-trial changes. This can be studied by manipulating the participant's perception while keeping the task requirement constant. We suggest for example an experiment in which the strategy selection is monitored during multiple stepping down trials from an illusory height difference. The illusion creates a disparity between the expected and actual stepping down height difference, which results in suboptimal strategy selection for the actual step height. If this deviation is noticed by the motor system (i.e., less successful), it should adjust the strategy selection in the following trials to adhere to the actual task requirements.

7.2.5 Do adequate movement choices lead to safer behaviour?

Following the theoretical framework in chapter 1 (Figure 1.1), the framework prescribes that inadequate movement choice leads to a smaller probability of successfully executing a task (i.e., $P(\text{success})$). A decreased $P(\text{success})$ leads to an increased probability that stability is jeopardised, and therefore, increases the occurrence of balance loss or falls. However, the results in chapter 6, showed that the adequacy of the movement selection did not predict fall risk in older adults.

To understand this finding, we need to take one step back and inspect the

Figure 7.2: Scheme of how falls relate to the experimentally measured strategy selection.

proposed and studied chain (Figure 7.2) that relate strategy selection to falls. The strategy selection during a stepping-down task was studied in an experimental setting, in which we instructed the participant to perform multiple steps down. Thereby, we assumed that this would give an insight into the behavioural choices in daily life (Figure 7.2, arrow *I*). The behavioural choice is weighted by the actual ability and the true task requirement (see framework Figure 1.1) and determines the probability of success (Figure 7.2, arrow *II*). This probability of success is the reciprocal of the chance of erroneous movement. Part of the erroneous movements lead to balance losses that can still be recovered; however, more strenuous errors can lead to falls (Figure 7.2, arrow *III*).

Yet, we do not know how strong these associations (depicted by the arrows in the scheme) are. For example, our results in chapter 3 demonstrated the task-specific nature of the degree of misjudgment. Likewise, the movement choice may be as task-specific as this degree of misjudgment. As such, experimentally assessed strategy selection might not (entirely) transfer to behavioural choices in daily life (Figure 7.2, arrow *I*). For the arrows in this chain, the strength of the associations (i.e., arrows) has not yet been established. Hence, to better understand how adequate movements are selected, we should discover the strengths of these associations.

Recently, Weijer et al. (2018) used accelerometer data to extract measures of actual ability (i.e., gait quality assessed as the sample entropy of the acceleration data) and perceived ability (i.e., perceived gait stability assessed by both FESi, and step length derived from the acceleration data) in 272 older adults. The use of accelerometers allowed them to evaluate the discrepancy between actual and perceived ability in relation to falls in daily life situations. Hence, reflecting on the scheme in Figure 7.2, they achieved to discard the first step (i.e., experimental assessment of the strategy selection) of the chain. Therefore, they excluded the uncertainty related to the association (i.e., arrow *I*). This was visible in their results as they concluded that the association between falls and gait quality was modified by the older adult's perceived gait ability. From their result, we infer that the pathways of how the discrepancy between perceived and actual ability lead via movement choice to a probability of success, described in the initial theoretical framework described in chapter 1, might exist.

7.3 Clinical and Scientific implications

The studies described in this thesis aimed to understand the interplay between perceived and actual ability and how this leads to the movement selection in older

adults. We suggested 1) the discrepancies between perceived and actual ability to be larger in an older age group, and 2) the consequences of inadequate motor behaviour to be larger in this age group. In that respect, this thesis on motor behaviour also provides us with some lessons for clinical practices or other research fields.

7.3.1 Clinical implications

In chapter 4, we found that older adults selected strategies that were not dictated by their actual ability. This might be due to an imprecise representation of their actual abilities, as described in chapter 2. Although there is no clinical test available yet that objectively quantify the adequacy of movement selection, we showed in chapter 3 that there are individuals who select behaviour that is not within the boundaries of their actual ability (i.e., the individuals that placed their foot inside the ‘river’ or being overly cautious). Therefore, we suggest that clinicians or therapists should bear in mind that there are older adults that may encounter difficulties selecting adequate behaviour. Especially, when one suspects a patient to 1) overestimate his or her relatively low physical abilities, or 2) being overly cautious with average physical abilities, it might be advisable to evaluate and discuss the intensity, complexity and perceived threat of daily life tasks. However, clinicians and therapists should be aware that a patient’s (mis)judgment is to a large extent task-specific (chapter 3, see also Weijer et al. (2019)) and context-specific (chapter 5).

Besides the potentially devastating physical consequences of a fall in older adults, often falls are accompanied by a substantial increase in the experienced fear of falling. This fear of falling may lead to activity avoidance (Delbaere et al., 2004), and as hypothesised in chapter 5 may lead to inappropriate movement selection. Our results showed that fear induced by a postural threat leads to an adjustment of the strategy selection. It has been argued that the fear induced by such postural threat is related to the fear that older adults experience when they are afraid of falling (Brown et al., 2002). When assessing the patient’s movement and motor ability, clinicians and therapists may incorporate the potential influence of fear, as movement selection is coupled to fear of falling in older adults (chapter 5). Hence, the fear regarding the possibility to fall might hamper the selection of appropriate movement selection and finally lead to a decrease in the probability of success.

In this thesis, we chose to determine the misjudgment on stepping and gait tasks, which are very common within the range of daily activities that our participants perform. Initially, we had chosen these tasks as we believed they would

give a glance into the participant's overall misjudgment. However, our analysis revealed the task-specificity of the misjudgment. Therefore, we suggest for future studies with the objective to determine the risk of balance loss due to levels of misjudgment to first evaluate the feasibility of examining the perceived and actual ability on a multitude of daily life tasks.

7.3.2 Scientific implications

Movement activities can be regarded as an accumulation of movement actions, and therefore, operate at longer time scales. Although in our experimental studies, we investigated solely the short-term movement behaviour (e.g., stepping down a height difference), the introduced framework may also apply to different time scales. This is extremely evident for example in the 'route preview' phase in free climbing. In an extreme sport like this, it is important to judge whether the planned activity – consisting of an ordered combination of task requirements – lies within reach of the actual ability. In the 'route preview' phase, the athlete identifies a climbing route and determines how all movement actions should be orchestrated to overcome the requirements of the ascent (Orth et al., 2016). Hence, this hints that our proposed framework might be applicable to the activity time-scale. Again, the same principle is relevant to movement planning in older adults. Movement navigation often entails a combination of multiple smaller motor tasks. Similar to the route previewing in free climbing, movement navigation requires the concatenation of motor planning of ordered tasks. Strolling around the city centre of Amsterdam might be challenging for older adults, as one needs to cross loose bricks, walk on uneven pavement, dodge cyclist, while avoiding approaching non-attentive pedestrians.

7.4 Conclusion

This thesis postulates that moving safely requires the ability to judge whether the biomechanical constraints can be overcome by the motor system. This entails that humans should have a valid and robust perception of their own physical ability. From the series of methods and paradigms that we developed and evaluated to assess the interplay between perceived and actual ability, our collective results showed that the majority of the fit and healthy older adults that we assessed do not align their perceived and actual ability in tasks that may lead to balance loss or even falls (i.e., walking and stepping tasks). From the combination of these tasks it also appeared that the discrepancy between perceived and actual ability is strongly task-dependent, which makes it very difficult to establish a person's

misjudgment in one single/general measure. Moreover, a more challenging task makes older adults adapt their perceived ability (i.e., anticipatory behaviour in terms of movement-strategy selection) to match the challenging context. This may have implications for older adults who experience fear in non-challenging situations, as they are likely to adjust their behaviour to their perceived threat. Such behavioural adjustments may, therefore, lead to inadequate motor strategies. Hence, the results address once again the importance of incorporating task context in order to understand how movement behaviour is shaped. While the perceived ability and the resulting movement behaviour may be detached from the actual ability in some individuals, it did not seem to contribute to the increased fall risk in older adults. However, further investigations are needed to fully understand the mechanisms of how the interplay between perceived and actual ability lead to inadequate behaviour, and whether this induces balance loss or even falls over short and longer terms. These findings allow me to conclude that over- or under-estimation is not likely to be a human trait, but rather a complex manifestation of multiple psychological facets that may lead to undesired movement behaviour in some daily activities or tasks.

Chapter 8

Samenvatting

De kunst van het selecteren van adequate bewegingen

Om onszelf veilig te verplaatsen in onze dagelijkse omgeving is het noodzakelijk om die omgeving goed waar te nemen. Om bijvoorbeeld een stoep op te stappen, is de informatie over de locatie en de hoogte van de stoeprand essentieel. Deze informatie wordt vervolgens door ons zenuwstelsel geïntegreerd en gebruikt bij het bewegen door de omgeving. Echter, er is nog weinig bekend over hoe mensen bewegingen selecteren, en de wetenschap heeft nog geen grip op *de kunst van het selecteren van adequate bewegingen*.

Met het toenemen van de leeftijd blijft het functioneren van het bewegingsapparaat niet onaangedaan; zo nemen onder andere spiermassa en spierkracht, maar ook de kwaliteit van de sensorische waarneming geleidelijk af. Met deze fysieke achteruitgang moeten ouderen rekening houden wanneer ze zich veilig door de omgeving willen bewegen. Dit inschattingsvermogen kan ook aangedaan zijn door cognitieve achteruitgang die optreedt bij veroudering. Ouderen bij wie deze inschatting onvoldoende is, kiezen wellicht gedrag dat niet past bij hun huidige fysieke gesteldheid. In het voorbeeld van de stoeprand: wanneer ouderen correct waarnemen hoe hoog de stoeprand is, kan elk van hen ook voor zichzelf een adequate inschatting maken of ze in het bezit zijn van voldoende motorische vaardigheden om veilig de stoep op te stappen?

Ouderen die zichzelf over-of onderschatten, met name in taken die uitdagend zijn voor de balans zoals tijdens lopen, zouden wellicht vaker inadequate bewegingen selecteren. In het geval dat iemand zijn motorische vaardigheden overschat kan het gebeuren dat deze persoon meer van zijn of haar lichaam vraagt dan dat wat fysiek mogelijk is, wat tot gevaarlijke situaties kan leiden. Aan de andere kant van dit spectrum kan iemand die zijn capaciteiten onderschat, bijvoorbeeld door de angst om te vallen, besluiten om bepaalde activiteiten niet meer te ondernemen.

Een verminderde inschattingsvermogen zou dus een verklaring kunnen zijn voor vallen bij ouderen.

Het doel van dit proefschrift was om methodieken en paradigma's te ontwikkelen die het inschattingsvermogen in kaart konden brengen en te onderzoeken wat de invloed van het inschattingsvermogen op het beweeggedrag is, zodat we beter begrijpen hoe adequate bewegingen worden geproduceerd.

In **hoofdstuk 2** van dit proefschrift is een nieuwe maat geïntroduceerd om het inschattingsvermogen te kwantificeren. Met deze maat is het inschattingsvermogen van de fysieke loopvaardigheid van ouderen onderzocht. Onze verwachting was dat ouderen in meer of mindere mate hun loopvaardigheid over- of onderschatten. We vroegen 27 gezonde ouderen om een inschatting te geven van het smalst beloobbare (virtuele) pad waarbinnen ze dachten te kunnen lopen zonder erbuiten te stappen. Deze inschatting maakten ze door de breedte van een op de loopband geprojecteerd pad aan te passen met een draadloze computermuis. Vervolgens vroegen we de ouderen om daadwerkelijk op de loopband te lopen waarop we virtuele paden met variërende breedtes (0,12 m - 0,20 m) projecteerden. Per padbreedte onderzochten we hoe goed men in staat was om binnen het virtuele pad te blijven. Op deze manier konden we de smalst haalbare padbreedte van elke deelnemer identificeren door te berekenen bij welke breedte 90 procent van de gemaakte stappen binnen het pad zouden vallen. Vervolgens hebben we deze zelf-ingeschatte padbreedte vergeleken met de daadwerkelijk smalst beloobbare padbreedte. Om een indicatie te krijgen van de validiteit van de ontwikkelde maat hebben we ook onderzocht of het lopen op een smaller pad ook daadwerkelijk moeilijker was, en of de zelf-ingeschatte en daadwerkelijke smalst haalbare padbreedte associeerde met klinisch gehanteerde maten voor valrisico, zoals beenspierkracht en het zelf ingeschatte vertrouwen om niet te vallen.

De kans dat men buiten het pad stapt was groter naarmate het geprojecteerde pad smaller was en deelnemers met meer spierkracht in de kniestickekkers waren beter in staat om binnen een smaller pad te lopen dan de deelnemers met minder grote kniestickekkcracht. Er was geen sterke associatie tussen de zelf-ingeschatte padbreedte en het aangegeven vertrouwen om niet te vallen (gemeten met de FES-I), en ook niet tussen de zelf-ingeschatte padbreedte en de smalst beloobbare breedte. Dit laatste suggereert dat ouderen over het algemeen moeite hebben met het precies inschatten van loopvaardigheid. Naast een padbreedte-manipulatie, hebben we ook een snelheids-manipulatie onderzocht. Hierin vroegen we deelnemers om de hoogste loopsnelheid aan te geven waarop men dacht binnen een gegeven pad te kunnen lopen. Echter de resultaten toonden dat deze manipulatie niet afdoende is om het inschattingsvermogen te kwantificeren.

De uitkomsten van het hierboven beschreven experiment lokte de vraag uit hoe consistent het inschattingsvermogen is bij oudere mensen over verschillende stap-taken. In **hoofdstuk 3** onderzochten we daarom de consistentie van de misschatting over verschillende stap-taken in 9 jongere en 15 oudere deelnemers. Hiervoor werd eerst een aantal criteria voorgesteld waaraan een taak moet voldoen om de misschatting valide te kunnen kwantificeren. De resultaten van dit experiment toonden aan dat de misschatting niet consistent was tussen verschillende stap-taken, terwijl de afzonderlijke zelf-ingeschatte danwel daadwerkelijk vaardigheden wel correleerden tussen verschillende stap-taken. Dit suggereerde dat ze consistent zijn in het inschatten van hun fysieke vaardigheid, maar dat we geen consistentie in misschattingen over taken konden vinden.

In voorgaande hoofdstukken lag de focus op het kwantificeren van het inschattingsvermogen door dit expliciet te vragen. Hierin veronderstelden we bovendien dat dit inschattingsvermogen wordt meegenomen in het besluit om een bepaald bewegingspatroon te selecteren, terwijl hier nog geen evidentie voor was. Wanneer (sommige) oudere mensen inderdaad vallen vanwege een inschattingsfout bij een specifieke taak, dan zou er bij inschattingsfouten eerst inadequate beweeggedrag moeten optreden. In de hoofdstukken 4,5 & 6 kwantificeerden we het inschattingsvermogen op een impliciete manier onderzocht, door de bewegingsstrategieën tijdens het afstappen van een verhoging te observeren.

In **hoofdstuk 4** is onderzocht op welke manier 21 oudere mensen van een verhoging afstapten. Bij het afstappen beschikt men over twee afstapstrategieën. Zo kan er worden afgestapt middels een teen- of hiellanding. Een teenlanding is veiliger maar vergt een hoge inspanning, terwijl er voor een hiellanding minder inspanning nodig is maar deze is uitdagender in termen van balanscontrole. De (impliciete) keuze voor een teen- of hiellanding berust dus op een compromis tussen veiligheid en inspanning en is afhankelijk van zowel fysieke vaardigheden als de hoogte van de afstap. We vroegen onze deelnemers een aantal keer met een vaste snelheid over een platform te lopen en een hoogteverschil (zoals een stoeprand) af te stappen. De uitgevoerde strategieën (teen- of hiellanding) bij verschillende hoogteverschillen werden geregistreerd als een maat van het inschattingsvermogen. Om te onderzoeken of ouderen strategieën selecteerden die passen bij hun fysieke vaardigheden, hebben we de deelnemers ook op een onverwacht moment laten afstappen. Deze onverwachte afstap zorgt ervoor dat de bewegingsenergie van de deelnemer toeneemt, en als de deelnemer deze bewegingsenergie niet absorbeert dan resulteert dit in een val. De mate waarin energie geabsorbeerd werd reflecteerde de daadwerkelijke vaardigheid. Opnieuw maakten we de vergelijking tussen de zelf-ingeschatte vaardigheid (i.e., afstapstrategie bij een verwachte

afstap) en de daadwerkelijke vaardigheid (energie absorptie bij een onverwachte afstap). De afstapstrategie was niet geassocieerd met de daadwerkelijke vaardigheid, en dit suggereerde dat ouderen hun afstapstrategie niet uitkozen op basis van hun daadwerkelijke vaardigheden.

Het doel van **hoofdstuk 5** was om te onderzoeken of een balansbedreiging (zoals het afstappen op grotere hoogte) invloed heeft op de afstapstrategie. Strikt is een hoogte manipulatie een verhoging van de consequentie van het balansverlies; balansbedreiging is in deze een stilistisch middel. In dit experiment werden 24 oudere deelnemers gevraagd om een aantal keer over een platform met een hoogteverschil te lopen in twee condities: 1) gelijkvloers en 2) op een verhoging van 0,78 meter. De loopsnelheid werd opgelegd middels een lichtstrip naast de opstelling die zich verplaatste met een snelheid van 1,1 m/s in de looprichting. De opstelling op hoogte wekte een fysiologische opwinding (i.e., fysiologische arousal) op, en zorgde ervoor dat de deelnemer vaker afstapte met een teenlanding. Oudere mensen worden dus voorzichtiger naarmate de balansbedreiging toeneemt. Verder hebben we gekeken of angstige individuen op een andere manier reageren op een balansbedreiging dan hun minder angstige leeftijdsgenoten. In dit onderzoek hebben we dit niet kunnen vaststellen. Een mogelijke verklaring hiervoor is dat de manipulatie niet sterk genoeg was om hevige angst teweeg te brengen die de deelnemers onderscheidde.

In het laatste experimentele hoofdstuk (**hoofdstuk 6**) is onderzocht of inschatting op basis van de bewegstrategieën een toegevoegde waarde heeft voor het voorspellen van vallen in het dagelijks leven bij 55 ouderen. De inschattingsfout werd gekwantificeerd op basis van de afstapstrategie (i.e., zelf-ingeschatte vaardigheid) in combinatie met een samengestelde maat voor de daadwerkelijke vaardigheid. Deze samengestelde maat bestond uit 1) de maximale staplengte en 2) de maximale hoogte waarover men nog over een balk kan heen stappen. Na bepaling van de afstapstrategie en de samengestelde maat, hebben deelnemers over een periode van 10 maanden bijgehouden of en hoe vaak zij gevallen zijn. Onze resultaten lieten zien dat de inschattingsfout geen toegevoegde waarde had om vallen te voorspellen. Daarbij hebben we gevonden dat voor ons model – maar ook voor bestaande klinische modellen – de accuraatheid van het voorspellen van een val gering was.

Conclusie

Dit proefschrift heeft als uitgangspunt dat voor het veilig uitvoeren van een bewegtaak, de biomechanische eisen van deze taak binnen de grenzen van de motorische vaardigheden liggen. Voor een veilige uitvoering moet men dus een in-

schatting maken van de biomechanische eisen van de taak, én van de eigen fysieke vaardigheid. Zodra een van deze twee inschattingen niet adequaat is, wordt de taak sub-optimaal uitgevoerd. Gebeurt dit tijdens een looptaak, dan zou men uit balans kunnen raken en bij een grote verstoring zou dit zelfs kunnen resulteren in een val (met alle gevolgen van dien). De collectieve resultaten van dit proefschrift hebben laten zien dat een groot deel van de gezonde ouderen die we hebben onderzocht, niet in staat waren om een accurate inschatting te maken van hun motorische vaardigheden in taken die mogelijk tot balansverlies of zelfs een val kunnen leiden. Uit verscheidende beweegtaken die zijn onderzocht hebben we kunnen aantonen dat het verschil tussen de zelf-ingeschatte vaardigheid en de daadwerkelijke vaardigheid afhangt van de beweegtaak die wordt opgelegd. We kunnen dus stellen dat inschattingsfouten taakspecifiek zijn. Dit gegeven maakt het moeilijk, zo niet onmogelijk, om het inschattingsvermogen van een individu in één (overkoepelende) maat te vangen. Daarnaast hebben we aangetoond dat een uitdagende omgeving ook invloed heeft op het maken van een inschatting in termen van het selecteren van bewegestrategieën. Dit heeft mogelijk consequenties voor oudere mensen die angst voor vallen ervaren tijdens alledaagse beweegtaken. Door deze angst, óf juist het ontbreken daarvan, zouden ze mogelijk niet adequate aanpassingen kunnen maken in het bewegingspatroon. Ondanks het feit dat voor een groot deel van de oudere deelnemers de zelf-ingeschatte vaardigheid niet strookt met de daadwerkelijke vaardigheid, droeg de inschattingsfout niet bij aan het voorspellen van een val. De resultaten uit dit proefschrift steunen mij in de overtuiging dat over- en onderschatting geen karaktereigenschappen van ouderen zijn, maar eerder een manifestatie van verschillende context- en taakspecifieke psychologische facetten (e.g., ervaart de deelnemer druk? Is de deelnemer alert, bang of bezorgd?) die zouden kunnen leiden tot inadequaat beweeggedrag in verschillende beweegtaken in het dagelijks leven.

List of abbreviations

The following list gives a short description of the abbreviations used throughout this thesis, together with their units.

Abbreviation	Description and unit
95%CI	95% Credible interval
ABC	Activities-specific balance confidence scale [points]
AIC	Akaike's information criterion
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
BF ₁₀	Bayes factor (support for H ₁ over H ₀)
EDA	Electrodermal activity [μ S]
FESi	Falls efficacy scale international [points]
H ₁	Alternative hypothesis
H ₀	Null hypothesis
h _{cons}	Consistency of strategy selection [cm^{-1}]
h _{crit}	Critical switching height [m, cm]
HDI	Highest credible interval
ICC	Intraclass correlation coefficient
IQR	Interquartile range
JASP	Jeffreys's amazing statistics program
LED	Light emitting diode
LOO	Leave-one-out cross-validation
M	Mean
P(success)	Probability of successfully executing a movement
MMSE	Mini mental state examination [points]
Mdn	Median
mGES	Modified gait efficacy scale [points]
N	Sample size

n	Subset size
OSF	Open Science Framework
$P(\text{path})$	Probability of successfully stepping inside a projected path
P_{heel}	Probability of a heel landing
P_{toe}	Probability of a toe landing
QS	QuickScreen [points]
r	Correlation coefficient
SD	Standard deviation
SPM	Statistical parametric mapping
t	Time [second, hour, day, year]
TMT	Trail making task [s]
v_{act}	Actual maximal walking speed [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]
v_{perc}	Self-perceived maximal walking speed [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$]
WAIC	Watanabe-Akaike information criterion
$\text{Width}_{\text{perc}}$	Self-perceived minimal path width [m]
$\text{Width}_{\text{act}}$	Actual minimal path width [m]
x_{act}	Actual ability composite score
ΔEDA	within difference EDA [μS]
δ	Cohen's d
η_p^2	Partial eta squared
ρ	Spearman's Rho (rank correlation coefficient)

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Dankcode

```
1 function dankcode(input)
2 % Function to thank everyone that helped pulling N.Kluft
3 % through his PhD project.
4 % INPUT
5 %     input = Your relationship with N. Kluft {cell}
6 thanked = false;
7
8 for x = input
9     switch x
10        case 'Mirjam Pijnappels'
11            disp('Beste Mirjam, wat is het een eer om de eerste te mogen zijn
12                waarover je het votum uitspreekt. Ik ga de inspirerende wekelijkse
13                bijeenkomsten missen, waarin je me ontzettend enthousiasmeerde en
14                je, ondanks je drukke agenda, je toch altijd even de tijd nam om
15                even te bespreken hoe het thuis gaat.')
```

```

31         case 'student'
32             disp('Scan QR in figure 2')
33         end
34     end
35     WorkingAtUBC = uiinput('Are you working at UBC? (y/n)', 's');
36     if isequal(WorkingAtUBC, 'y')
37         disp('Thank you for the wonderful time in Vancouver!')
38     end
39     if ismember(x, ['Paranimf', 'Paranymph'])
40         disp('Roel en Rutger, ik vind het super dat ik samen met jullie het toneel
41             mag betreden!')
42     end
43     if ismember(x, ['Pa & Maria', 'Ma & JH', 'Oma Car & Janny', 'Noef & Wes', '
44         Palendino'])
45         disp('Lieve Oma Car, Oma Janny, Maria, JH, Noef en Wes, en Stinsie.
46             Dankjulliewel voor alle steun en liefde. Ik geniet en hou ontzettend
47             veel van jullie!
48             Padre y Madre, dank voor de geweldige jeugd en jullie steun en liefde! Ik
49             heb twee geweldige ouders; jullie zijn een prachtig voorbeeld voor deze
50             twee ouders in sp\{'e}')
51     elseif ismember(x, 'Opa Loek')
52         disp('Lieve lieve Luigi, Amigo, Padres Familias, lieve opa Loek. Helaas
53             heb je de geboorte van Moksi op een haar na gemist. Je stond altijd
54             klaar voor alles en iedereen. We ga je heel erg missen.')
55     elseif ismember(x, 'Moksi')
56         disp('Lieve Moksi, toen ik dit schreef was je er nog niet. Je naam was
57             zelfs nog geheim. Ik kijk er heel heel erg naar uit om je te
58             ontmoeten!')
59     elseif isequal(x, 'Melissa')
60         disp('Lieve baby, aan jou zijn de laatste woorden van dit proefschrift
61             gericht. Bedankt dat je er altijd voor me bent. De 7 jaar die ik samen
62             met je heb mogen delen waren niet te overschatten, Ik kijk uit naar wat
63             de komende jaren ons gaat brengen! I love you 4EVAH!')
64         t = linspace(-pi, pi, 350); X = t .* sin( pi * .872*sin(t)./t); Y = -abs(t)
65             .* cos(pi * sin(t)./t);
66         plot(X,Y); fill(X, Y, 'r'); axis square;set(gcf, 'Position', get(0,'
67             Screensize'));
68     end
69 end
70 end

```


Figure 1: SuperTanks!

Figure 2: Thankie!

Amsterdam
Movement
Sciences

Amsterdam Movement Sciences conducts scientific research to optimize physical performance in health and disease based on a fundamental understanding of human movement in order to contribute to the fulfillment of a meaningful life.